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Deliverable Abstract

This Annex to EOSC EDEN deliverable D2.1 presents the main scenarios, services and requirements for interoperability and exchange of Archival Information Packages (AIPs) in the EOSC EDEN project.

The scenarios for interoperability and exchange of APIs covered in this Annex include: the transfer of AIPs when custody and responsibility for their care is transferred between repositories and archives; replication of AIPs across multiple archives or storage services as part of business continuity and disaster recovery; and the ability to send AIPs in whole or in part to and from third-party LTDP services so that preservation actions can be applied to their contents.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
AIP	Archival Information Package
BCDR	Business Continuity and Disaster Recovery
BDBag	Big Data Bag
CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics
CCSDS	Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems
CTS	Core Trust Seal
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DPC RAM	Digital Preservation Coalition Rapid Assessment Model
EDEN	Enhancing Digital preservation strategies at European and National level
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC TF on LTDP	EOSC Task Force on Long Term Data Preservation
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
LTDP	Long Term Digital Preservation
METS	Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard
MOIMS-DAI	Mission Operations and Information Management Services Data Archive Interoperability
OAIS	Open Archival Information System
OAIS IF	OAIS Interoperability Framework
OAIS RM	OAIS Reference Model
OCFL	Oxford Common File Layout
PCDM	Portland Common Data Model
PREMIS	Preservation Metadata: Implementation Strategies

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

PDI	Preservation Description Information
RDA WG TRSP	RDA Working Group on trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers
RO-Crate	Research Object Crate
TDA	Trustworthy Digital Archive
TDR	Trustworthy Digital Repository
TTRAM	Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability, Technology
XFDU	XML Formatted Data Unit

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Landscape of Standards and Specifications for AIPs	3
2.1	OAIS Information Model	5
3	Methodology	8
4	Scenarios	10
5	Considerations	12
6	Aspects and Attributes	13
7	Services and Requirements	15
7.1	Services for Describing AIPs	15
7.2	Services for Validating AIPs	17
7.3	Services for Exchanging AIPs	19
7.4	Services for AIP Cross-walks and Transformations	20
7.5	Detailed Requirements Analysis	20
7.6	Summary of AIP Services	22
8	Outlook and Next Steps	25
9	Acknowledgements	27
10	References	28

List of Figures

Figure 2.1	AIP Structure: Information Model, Serialisation, and Containers	3
Figure 2.1.1	OAIS Information Packages (Reproduced from the OAIS specification) [R1]	5
Figure 2.1.2	OAIS AIP Structure (Reproduced from the OAIS specification) [R1]	6
Figure 3.1	Information gathering for AIP interoperability and exchange	8
Figure 3.2:	Process used to go from considerations to service specifications	9
Figure 7.1:	Example of how EDEN AIP Services can be combined	23

List of Tables

Table 2.2:	AIP Structure: Information Model, Serialisation, and Containers	3
Table 4.1:	Scenarios for AIP Interoperability and Exchange	11
Table 5.1:	Considerations for AIP Interoperability and Exchange	12
Table 6.1:	Aspects and Attributes for AIP Interoperability and Exchange	14
Table 7.1.1:	AIP Services for Packaging Information	16
Table 7.1.2:	Requirements for the AIP Packaging Information Services	17
Table 7.2.1:	Services for Validating AIPs	19

Table 7.2.2: Requirements for AIP Validation Services	19
Table 7.3.1: AIP Exchange Service	20
Table 7.3.2: Requirements for AIP Exchange Service	20
Table 7.5.1: Requirement Sources	22

Executive Summary

This Annex to the EOSC EDEN deliverable D2.1 [R31] presents the main scenarios, services and requirements for interoperability and exchange of Archival Information Packages (AIPs) in the EOSC EDEN project.

The term AIP originates in the well known and widely followed Open Archive Information Systems (OAIS) reference model. In OAIS, AIPs are considered as internal packages that are held and managed within an archive. They are a critical part of the OAIS Information Model and they are essential for long term digital preservation because they are intended to contain not only the digital objects that need to be preserved but also all of the information needed to be able to preserve and provide access to those digital objects in the future. This includes the structure and semantics of the digital objects plus information on their identifiers, context, fixity, provenance and rights. Collectively this allows for the digital objects in an AIP to be managed by the archive and preservation actions to be applied so that the digital objects remain usable over time.

Whilst AIPs in OAIS are primarily internal to an archive, there are several important scenarios where AIPs need to be externalised by an archive and exchanged with external entities such as other archives or third-party providers of Long Term Digital Preservation (LTDP) services. Scenarios include: transfer of AIPs so that custody and responsibility for their care is transferred between repositories and archives; replication of AIPs across multiple archives or storage services as part of business continuity and disaster recovery; and the ability to send AIPs in whole or in part to third-party LTDP services so that preservation actions can be applied to their contents. These scenarios are explored further in this Annex.

However, whilst OAIS describes the information that needs to be held in an AIP and how that information is organised, in practice there are a wide range of approaches taken to the implementation of AIPs by different organisations, domains, disciplines and preservation system providers. This leads to a series of challenges for AIP interoperability and exchange. Some of these include: a lack of well defined machine-readable semantics for AIP content; a diverse range of formats and specifications used for AIP implementation; a lack of consistent approach to implementing the OAIS Information Model for AIPs; and a lack of a well defined mechanism for exchanging AIPs between organisations and systems. These challenges and a proposed solution for EOSC EDEN are explored in this Annex.

This Annex is intended to be a self-contained document that can be read on its own without needing to read EDEN Deliverable D2.1 [R31] beforehand. As a result, this Annex contains some content that is already contained in D2.1, it contains extensions to this content such as a more in depth requirements analysis, and it contains additional content such as a more detailed analysis of the landscape of existing standards and specifications for constructing and describing AIPs.

1 Introduction

This report considers scenarios where AIPs need to be externalised from a Trustworthy Digital Archive (TDA) and exchanged with other entities. These entities could be other TDAs, third-party providers of Long Term Digital Preservation (LTDP) services, end users (consumers in OAIS terminology), or organisations involved in external assessment of whether the TDA is implementing good practices for LTDP.

AIPs are an OAIS concept as described by the OAIS Information Model [R1]. The aim of AIPs is to capture and organise all the information needed to both describe digital objects and enable their ongoing preservation and access.

There are several interoperability and exchange scenarios for AIPs that include: transfer of AIPs when custody and responsibility for their care is transferred between repositories and archives; replication across multiple archives or storage services as part of business continuity and disaster recovery; and the ability to send AIPs in whole or in part to third-party LTDP services so that preservation actions can be applied.

The ability to externalise content from a TDA as a well-defined package that can be mapped to established standards such as OAIS also helps to support transparency of TDA holdings and assessment by third parties. Third-parties include external assessors of the TDA, for example under CoreTrustSeal, who want to see evidence that the TDA is following good practices and that the TDA is holding the information needed in order to properly preserve and manage its content. Third-parties also potentially include users of the content who want to assess its quality and trustworthiness by inspecting the information held in AIPs (although it should be noted that in the OAIS model, access to archive content for consumers is not normally done by providing direct access to AIPs and instead is usually done by creating DIPs that contain the specific information that the consumer needs).

The use of AIPs are not a mandatory part of LTDP good practice, for example the use of AIPs does not explicitly feature in models and guidelines such as DPC RAM [R2], the NDSA Levels of Preservation [R4], or CoreTrustSeal [R3]. However, many of the information types and processes that do feature in these models and guidelines are included in the OAIS model. Examples include checksums, file formats, characterisation, validation, normalisation, packaging, preservation metadata and so on. The terminology used by models and guidelines for LTDP good practice is not always the same as that used by OAIS, but the OAIS Information Model can be used to represent the objects that are being preserved, their semantics and characteristics, and the provenance and results of the preservation actions that have been applied to them.

Some form of implementation of AIPs is widely used by archives for their content, i.e. they package up their holdings in one way or another. Many LTDP systems, both commercial and open source, provide some form of implementation of AIPs and will claim they conform to the OAIS model. However, the reality is that AIPs as implemented by TDAs are not always fully conformant with the OAIS information model. Sometimes this is because of misunderstandings of OAIS by vendors and systems developers and sometimes this is because of incomplete implementation of the OAIS model in tools and systems they use. But more commonly, it can simply be the case that not all the information required by OAIS is available to a TDA and as a result its AIPs are imperfect (according to OAIS), incomplete or will evolve over time as more information becomes available. This brings with it requirements for packages and their contents to be versioned and updatable so that AIPs can be constructed and extended over time. The reality of AIPs in the real world that have incomplete contents and/or grow and change over time means that there is also an opportunity to use the OAIS Information Model as a measure of 'completeness' and hence as a way to look for gaps and missing information in a TDA's holdings.

The practicalities of doing digital preservation in an imperfect world means that a wide range of approaches are taken to AIP implementation by different organisations, domains, disciplines and preservation system providers. This leads to a series of challenges for AIP interoperability and exchange. Some of these challenges include: a lack of well defined machine-readable semantics for AIP content; a diverse range of formats and specifications used for AIP implementation; a lack of consistent approach to implementing the OAIS Information Model for AIPs; and a lack of a well defined mechanism for exchanging AIPs between organisations and systems.

Whilst many challenges exist, the end objective of being able to efficiently exchange machine-readable and interoperable packages of information (AIPs) between TDAs, LTDP services and other organisations and systems is an important one. AIPs are not the only way to do this, but building a set of services in EDEN that are based on the OAIS Information Model is very much an opportunity to establish common semantics and far better interoperability than is currently achieved between today's TDAs and LTDP services.

The key to success is accommodating and building upon the wide range of standards and specifications that are already available for structuring and describing digital objects in EOSC rather than trying to displace them or enforce or mandate a single common standard. Instead, the approach should be to augment and build upon this existing landscape by using the OAIS Information Model and its semantics (more specifically through OAIS Packaging Information as discussed later). The rest of this report details the approach taken and the resulting services that have been identified.

This Annex is structured as follows.

1. The Landscape section explores the current standards and specifications in use for describing and packaging content in TDAs.
2. The Methodology section describes the approach taken to establishing the set of AIP services needed in EOSC EDEN and the requirements they need to satisfy for AIP interoperability and exchange.
3. The Scenarios section describes the main problems that we are attempting to solve.
4. The Considerations and Aspects section describes the challenges that are faced in delivering a workable solution and the differing aspects of that solution.
5. The Services and Requirements presents a set of AIP interoperability and exchange services and the requirements that they need to meet.
6. The Next Steps section describes work that will follow, in particular service specifications and implementation.

2 Landscape of Standards and Specifications for AIPs

The definitive specification of an AIP is the OAIS Information Model. However, because OAIS only provides a logical model and not guidelines for implementation, a wide range of additional standards and specifications are in use, or can be applied, when constructing and describing AIPs and their contents.

The diagram below shows the typical anatomy of an AIP and some of the relevant standards and specifications that can be involved.

Figure 2.1 AIP Structure: Information Model, Serialisation, and Containers

The OAIS Information Model describes the logical contents of the AIP. OAIS does not mandate an implementation, for example it does not say how an AIP should be serialised and stored. This is reasonable given that AIPs are typically internal to an archive and the organisation holding them will want to make its own decisions on the most appropriate way to manage the information they contain, for example using databases for metadata, storage servers for digital objects held in files, deployment on premise or in the cloud and so on.

However, when externalised from an archive for exchange or storage, the contents of the AIP will need to be serialised in some way, for example so the files and metadata in the AIP can be exchanged with an external entity such as another TDA. The serialised AIP may optionally be packaged in some form of container that facilitates transfer (e.g. a zipped Bagit bag). This leads to the three-layer model shown in the diagram above.

AIP layer	Description
Information Model	Logical structure and contents of the information package, for example as defined by the OAIS Information Model
Serialisation	Implementation of the logical model in a form that can be stored or transmitted. Includes metadata (e.g. representation information and PDI), bitstreams (e.g. files), organisation (e.g. folders), and linking between metadata and bitstreams.
Container	All or part of a package is held in a container format that is used for transfer or storage.

Table 2.2: AIP Structure: Information Model, Serialisation, and Containers

There are many options for serialisation of both metadata and data within an AIP. Some options are explicitly designed to align with the OAIS reference model such as E-ARK and include standards from the digital preservation and archiving community such as METS and PREMIS. Other options are more focused on Research Data such as RO-Crate and may use research data oriented metadata standards such as DCAT or DataCite. Some options only address specific aspects of serialisation. For example, OCFL is a way of organising and versioning package contents and allows for inventories of the files in a package, but it has nothing to say about how metadata is included in the package. Optionally, an serialised AIP may be held in a container to facilitate exchange, for example a zip file or a Bagit bag. Several of the standards and specifications listed can be combined. For example, E-ARK uses PREMIS and METS.

Some of the standards relevant to creating information packages and hence AIPs include:

- [Open Archival Information Model \(OAIS\)](#). [R1] OAIS was updated in Dec 2024. The current version is M3.
- OAIS Interoperability Framework (OAIS-IF). [R5][R6]. This is a new OAIS standard that is currently under development and includes how OAIS AIPs can be serialised and exchanged.
- [E-ARK SIP, AIP, DIP](#) [R7] from DILCIS. E-ARK includes a [Common Specification for Information Packages](#) (CSIP) and domain specific [Content Information Type Specifications](#) (CTIS).
- [XFDU](#) [R8] is a CCSDS specification for packaging data and metadata and can be used for OAIS packages, e.g. as used by [SAFE \(Standard Archive Format for Europe\)](#) for Earth Observation data.
- [OCFL](#) (Oxford Common File Layout) [R9] for organising the contents of a package into files and folders, including inventories and versioning information.
- [Moab](#) [R10] from Stanford as an approach to Digital Object versioning.
- [PCDM](#) [R12] (Portland Common Data Model) for describing the way content in the package is structured into Collections, Objects and Files.
- [RO-Crate](#) [R11] as a way to describe Research Objects
- [BDBag](#) [R13] and [Bagit](#) [R14] (note latest Bagit is V1.0, most people use/reference the somewhat older V0.97 version)
- [FAIR Digital Objects](#) [R15] and the [FAIR Digital Object Framework](#) (FDOF) [R16]
- [ReproZip](#) [R17] and other models for packaging both software and data.
- [METS](#) [R18] as a container format for metadata (dmdSec and amdSec) and as a way to describe the structure (StructMaps) of digital content
- [PREMIS](#) [R19] as a preservation metadata standard, for example allowing records (provenance) to be made of digital preservation actions in the form of events.
- [DCAT](#) [R20], [DDI](#) [R21], [DataCite](#) [R22] and a myriad of domain and discipline specific metadata standards for research data (e.g. DarwinCore, FITS, SnowmedCT etc. just to name a few).

The objective of the list above is not to be exhaustive but rather to illustrate the diversity of standards and specifications that can be used and combined when creating self-describing packages of information. For example, the [Archivematica](#)¹ system creates AIPs that combine Bagit, METS and PREMIS. There is an [RO profile for BDBag](#)² which combines RO-Crate with Bagit. [LDaCA](#)³ combines RO-Crate and OCFL. And E-ARK AIPs use METS and PREMIS, can be implemented in combination with OCFL, and be contained within Bagit bags.

The examples above illustrate that it is not feasible for EDEN to impose a single AIP specification on TDAs, e.g. by mandating that all EDEN AIPs must follow E-ARK. This is why the EDEN approach, as described further below in the section: [Services for Describing AIPs](#), is to use OAIS Packaging Information as a way to augment

¹ Archivematica digital preservation software from Artefactual Ltd. <https://www.archivematica.org/en/>

² Research Object profile for Big Data bags: <https://github.com/ResearchObject/bagit-ro>

³ Language Data Commons Australia: <https://www.ldaca.edu.au/about/technologies/>

and describe existing AIPs so that they can be compared with, and assessed against, the OAIS Information Model and understood in a machine-readable way when exchanged.

2.1 OAIS Information Model

This section briefly describes AIPs as defined by the OAIS Information Model from the Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS). This establishes the OAIS terminology used in the rest of this document (e.g. Representation Information, PDI etc.).

The OAIS Information Model defines three types of information package: SIP, AIP and DIP as shown below:

Figure 4-17: Information Package Taxonomy

Figure 2.1.1 OAIS Information Packages (Reproduced from the OAIS specification) [R1]

Of these, the AIP is the most extensive and it is a requirement for OAIS conformance for it to contain both Representation Information (e.g. the structure and semantics of the digital objects that it contains) and Preservation Description Information (PDI).

The structure of an AIP is shown below. The main concepts of an AIP are that:

- One or more **Digital Objects**, which will typically mean files but can also be individual bitstreams, are described by **Representation Information**. The Representation Information describes the structure and the semantics of the Digital Objects.
- A Digital Object is also described using **Preservation Description Information (PDI)**, which in turn contains **Reference Information** (e.g. Identifiers used to refer to the contents of the AIP), **Context Information** (how the contents of the AIP are related to an external environment, for example external objects or sources of information), **Fixity Information** (e.g. checksums), **Access Rights Information** (e.g. rights to both preserve and provide access to the contents) and **Provenance Information** (e.g. the history of the content, both before ingest into an archive or repository and all the preservation actions and processes that have subsequently been applied).
- **Content Information** (Representation Information and Digital Objects) and PDI is then packaged together into the **Archive Information Package (AIP)**.
- The complete contents of the AIP is both described by and delimited by **Packaging Information**, which describes how all the components of the AIP are logically and physically bound together. In a sense, Packaging Information is both an inventory of the contents of the AIP and a description for how to interpret each one.

- A **Package Description** is also provided as a finding aid for the AIP contents, i.e. it is an index for the AIP that aids with discovery of the contents, for example containing descriptive metadata.

Figure 4-21: Archival Information Package (Detailed View) and Its Associated Package Description and Packaging Information

Figure 2.1.2 OAIS AIP Structure (Reproduced from the OAIS specification) [R1]

OAIS Packaging Information is a particularly important concept for this Annex because it provides a mechanism for describing the contents and semantics of an AIP. It does not contain the actual contents of the AIP, e.g. the digital objects, rather it is a way of describing how the AIP is structured, what standards and specifications are being used, how the components of the AIP are connected together and so on. OAIS Packaging Information is itself an OAIS Information Object, which means it can contain its own Digital Objects and associated Representation Information. This allows Packaging Information to be self-describing.

The OAIS Information Model provides a way to build up and describe information packages at multiple levels (e.g. all the way from bitstreams in files and details of file formats through to high level constructs with defined structure and semantics). However, it is not the objective to hold absolutely everything in an AIP. An assumption is made that the community of users for AIP contents (the Designated Community) has some understanding of its domain that can be used when receiving and understanding AIP contents. In OAIS this is called the Knowledge Base of the Designated Community. This external knowledge base is important and from a practice perspective includes things like ontologies, vocabularies, schemas, specifications and so on. Therefore, an important aspect of machine-readable AIPs is the ability to connect and link them to this external

knowledge base, for example using Linked Data techniques. This can be done both within the AIPs using PDI, e.g. Context Information and Other Representation Information, and in the Packaging Information, e.g. to describe what metadata standards and schemas are being used.

It should also be noted that OAIS terminology is not exactly aligned with similar terminology used by both other digital preservation standards (e.g. PREMIS) or by EOSC and EDEN (especially the term Digital Object which has a much broader meaning in EOSC than it does in OAIS). In this Annex we use OAIS terminology.

The OAIS Information Model has seen several revisions over a 25 year period and is relatively mature. The CCSDS is now looking at a new set of specifications for interoperability and exchange of information packages. This comes under the banner of the OAIS Interoperability Framework (OAIS IF) [R5]. An overview is available in [New Standards for Archive and Information Interoperability: A Digital Preservation Perspective \(2023\) \[R5\]](#)

The OAIS IF work is very much under development. OAIS IF specifications and implementations have not been released outside of the MOIMS-DAI (Mission Operations and Information Management Services Data Archive Interoperability) working group. However, some of this work will likely be relevant to EDEN and the author is already in discussions with David Giarretta about this. In particular, a JSON schema for OAIS Information Packages is under development [R6], which may be relevant to the development of a OAIS Packaging Information specification for EDEN (see later in this document).

3 Methodology

A wide range of inputs were sought when identifying the approach that should be taken in EOSC EDEN to AIP interoperability and exchange. These are shown in the diagram below.

Figure 3.1 Information gathering for AIP interoperability and exchange

The inputs include:

- EOSC initiatives such as the EOSC Interoperability Framework and recommendations from the EOSC Task Force on Long Term Data Preservation
- Requirements from the EDEN and FIDELIS projects such as the Core Preservation Processes [R29] from EDEN WP1 and the TTRAM matrix [R23] from FIDELIS.
- A review of the landscape of existing standards and specifications for AIPs and Research Data packaging. This list is long and examples include OAIS, E-ARK, OCFL, RO-Crate, XFDU and others.
- The long-term requirements for FAIR data to remain so over time and to be held in Trusted Digital Repositories with assessment against CoreTrustSeal.
- Scenarios and business cases that involve AIP interoperability and exchange because this is a major focus of the EDEN project which aims to develop a set of services to support LTDP in EOSC.

The inputs above feed into a process that delivers a series of considerations, aspects, attributes, services, requirements and ultimately specifications. This process is shown below and explained in more detail in D2.1.

In this process:

- **Considerations** are challenges or problems that need to be addressed
- **Aspects** are the different dimensions of the solution
- **Services** are specific areas of functionality that is needed

- These services need to meet a set of specific **Requirements**
- The existence of the services, for example as provided by a given TDA, can be identified and assessed using **Attributes**
- The combination of services, requirements and attributes feeds into the detailed **Specifications** of those services.

The output of the process is a set of specifications that are sufficiently detailed to enable development work to be done.

Figure 3.2: Process used to go from considerations to service specifications

Whilst the process shown above appears somewhat linear, in practice it was more iterative, for example with initial services identified shortly after the information gathering stage which were then refined after more detailed analysis of considerations, aspects and requirements.

The outcome of each stage is documented in the rest of this Annex.

4 Scenarios

The following scenarios were identified for AIP interoperability and exchange. These define the scope for the more detailed analysis and specification work that was done afterwards.

Scenario	Description
Exchange of AIPs between organisations and systems	<p>AIPs can be used as part of lossless exchange of content between TDAs and LTDP environments. Reasons for transfer of AIPs between repositories or preservation systems include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transfer of custody from one repository or archive to another, for example if a repository is no longer capable of being the custodian of some or all of its holdings. • Migration of content between LTDP environments, for example is a new digital preservation system is being installed to replace an old one. • Replication of content across multiple repositories, for example in a LOCKSS⁴ [R30] type approach where multiple organisations hold a copy of the same content for redundancy and resilience.
AIPs as part of Business Continuity and Disaster Recovery (BCDR)	<p>Serialisation of content into AIPs that are then stored outside of a repository's main systems can form an important element of business continuity and disaster recovery. If a major failure or outage occurs in the main systems (for example, data centre disaster, ransomware, supplier goes out of business etc.), then a set of AIPs in an independent location can be used as part of recovery from the disaster. This is because the AIPs are self-describing and should contain all the information needed to understand the content within them and to continue the digital preservation of that content.</p> <p>This is sometimes called establishing a 'fire break'⁵. If the whole repository 'burns down', then the AIPs in the external location should be unaffected, which then allows for recovery.</p>
AIPs as evidence of following good practice for LTDP	<p>Holding content in AIPs is not mandated by most models of good practice for digital preservation. Instead, good practice for LTDP tends to focus on the processes that should be followed (for example the Core Preservation Processes identified in EDEN) and the information that those processes create or consume. As defined in OAIS, an AIP should contain content information (e.g. the data and metadata that is the subject of preservation) and a full set of Preservation Description Information (e.g. identifiers, checksums, rights, provenance etc.). This means an AIP both provides a record of the preservation processes that have been followed (e.g. provenance) and contains the artefacts of those preservation processes (e.g. file format identifiers, metadata from characterisation, normalised files). This in turn means that AIPs can be used to provide evidence that a TDA has applied LTDP good practice. The content they contain and the fact that they exist (or can be constructed) can provide assurance that good practice is being followed.</p>

⁴ LOCKSS = Lots Of Copies Keep Stuff Safe. The LOCKSS Program at Stanford Libraries provides open-source technologies and services for high-confidence, resilient, secure digital preservation
<https://www.lockss.org/>

⁵ A fire break is a technique used to stop the spread of forest fires. In digital preservation, this term or ones like it such as 'air gap' are used to describe isolation of systems so that major faults or data corruption or loss are limited in their spread.
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Firebreak>

AIPs as evidence of a sufficient Information Model	<p>In OAIS, an AIP is part of the OAIS Information Model. This is a logical model that describes the information that should be managed / retained in an archive that conforms to OAIS. For example, an AIP should contain all the descriptive, structural, technical, administrative and technical metadata needed to fully understand the data in the AIP. This includes the semantics of the content plus supporting information such as checksums, file format information, a history of all preservation actions, licensing and rights and so on. Therefore, if a TDA implements AIPs that follow a recognised specification such as the OAIS Information Model, or if the TDA can show that its holdings conform to the requirements of the OAIS Information Model, then this can make it easier to assess whether a TDA is using an information model that is sufficient for LTDP.</p> <p>As described by David Giarretta⁶, who is one of the main authors of OAIS, "If an archive claims that it has Archival Information Packages (AIPs) then it must be able to identify, in whatever it calls its version of an AIP, all the various components which an OAIS AIP must have. If it cannot do this then it cannot be conformant to OAIS.". The converse is therefore true that if an archive can show that it holds all the required components of an AIP as defined by OAIS then it is holding sufficient information (according to OAIS) that is needed for preservation and use of its holdings.</p>
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Table 4.1: Scenarios for AIP Interoperability and Exchange

The first two scenarios are clear cases of where AIPs need to be externalized from a TDA so that they can be sent to a third-party, for example another TDA or an external digital preservation or archival storage service.

The second two scenarios are cases where having a well specified and interoperable way of describing AIPs can help with assessment of and trust in a repository or archive. This is an important role for AIPs and can also involve external entities. For example, the ability to produce AIPs in an externalized format that can be readily assessed against OAIS is likely to be helpful in TDA assessment by third-parties, for example under CoreTrustSeal. The ability to provide AIPs in an externalized format also enables external quality and conformance testing services to be applied. For example, users of AIP content in order may want to assess the quality and FAIRness of the AIP as part of understanding whether they can trust and reuse the content. Likewise, a TDA may want to use external services to assess its AIPs as a way of independently validating that it is holding what it needs to for long term digital preservation and to identify gaps. These scenarios are made much easier if AIPs can be serialized and described in a consistent and interoperable way.

⁶ See David Giarretta's book Essential Digital Preservation as provided on the OAIS community wiki http://community.oais.info/Main/WebHome#Essential_Digital_Preservation_45_free_book

5 Considerations

The main challenge with AIP interoperability and exchange is a lack of common approaches and standards across TDAs. Furthermore, attempting to enforce or mandate a single standardised approach is highly likely to fail due to the very wide range of data formats, standards and specifications that are used for the various components of an AIP, several of which can be discipline specific such as descriptive metadata, data structures and file formats.

Considerations include:

Consideration	Description	EOSC Interoperability Framework Level
Lack of well defined semantics for AIPs	Organisations use a wide range of formats, standards, schemas, vocabularies and ontologies for their holdings, many of which can be discipline specific. There is no consistent way for organisations to describe the semantics of their AIPs.	Semantic
Diverse range of formats and specifications used for AIPs	Organisations use a wide range of formats, specifications and structures for their data and metadata. There is no consistent way for organisations to describe the technical details of their AIPs, for example when they are exchanged.	Technical
Lack consistent approach to implementing the OAIS Information Model for AIPs	OAIS is one of the defacto standards for AIPs. However, OAIS is a logical Information Model and implementation is left up to the TDA that decides to follow it. This results in inconsistent or varied approaches and a difficulty in assessing AIPs against the OAIS Information Model.	Technical
Lack of well defined mechanism for exchanging AIPs between organisations and systems	There is not a well defined protocol and API for exchanging AIPs between TDAs, including where AIPs can use a range of standards and formats for their contents and may have multiple versions that evolve over time.	Technical
Machine readable rights for the Digital Preservation of AIPs	A TDA must have the legal basis for retaining AIP contents and applying preservation actions so that the contents remain usable over time. This includes any rights needed to enable AIPs to be transferred to third-parties, e.g. other TDAs or external preservation services.	Legal

Table 5.1: Considerations for AIP Interoperability and Exchange

6 Aspects and Attributes

The considerations identified in the previous section result in a set of aspects that need to be addressed. These are presented in the table below, including how they could be assessed through attributes:

Consideration	Aspect	Description	Attributes
Lack of well defined semantics for AIPs	Well defined semantics for each component of an AIP	There needs to be a mechanism that allows a TDA to describe each component of its AIPs in terms of the semantics that apply, for example which schemas, vocabularies and ontologies are being used. This includes the semantics of the data in the AIP, the semantics of associated information such as provenance, fixity, rights and quality, and the contents of the AIP as defined by the semantics of the OAIS Information Model.	The TDA can demonstrate what semantic standards and specifications it follows for its holdings. The TDA can describe its holdings according to the semantics of the OAIS Information model.
Lack of well defined semantics for AIPs	Evaluation of AIPs against the semantics of the OAIS Information Model	A TDA should be able to describe each component of its AIPs in terms of the OAIS Information Model so that the AIP can be evaluated for completeness and conformance to the OAIS information model. For example, which component of the AIP corresponds to PDI, Representation Information, Data Objects etc.	The TDA can map each component of its AIPs to a corresponding entity in the OAIS Information Model
Diverse range of formats and specifications used for AIPs	The technical details of each component of an AIP are well defined and at all levels.	There needs to be a mechanism that allows a TDA to describe each component of its AIPs in terms of the technical formats, specifications and standards that are used. For example, the formats used for metadata (e.g. JSON, CSV, XML etc), references to the schemas that apply (e.g. DataCite, DCAT etc.), the specifications used for layout (e.g. OCFL), the information package standards followed (e.g. E-ARK), the technical mapping to the OAIS Information Model, and how content is packaged for transfer (e.g. Bagit).	The TDA can describe the technical standards and specifications it follows for all aspects of serialising and packaging an AIP.
Lack consistent approach to implementing the OAIS Information Model for AIPs	Evaluation of AIP contents against the components of the OAIS Information Model	A TDA should be able to check the extent to which an AIP conforms to the OAIS Information Model from a technical perspective. This includes whether the mapping to OAIS is syntactically correct, whether the claimed components of the OAIS Information Model are physically present in the AIP, and for each component whether they are technically conformant to their specified formats and schemas.	The TDA can show to what extent its AIPs conform to the requirements of OAIS.

Lack of well defined mechanism for exchanging AIPs between organisations and systems	Exchange of AIPs between organisations	There should be a well defined protocol and set of API endpoints that can be used to request and execute transfer of AIPs in whole or in part between organisations. This includes support for AIP versioning and synchronisation of AIP versions between organisations.	The TDA supports access to and exchange of its AIPs using a defined protocol and set of APIs.
Machine readable rights for the Digital Preservation of AIPs	Machine readable rights specifications	Rights change over time and for a large number of AIPs the checks to ensure appropriate rights are in place can be burdensome. Therefore, rights statements need to be machine readable to support automated checks.	The TDA can automatically check and confirm it has the legal basis for holding and preserving its AIPs.

Table 6.1: Aspects and Attributes for AIP Interoperability and Exchange

7 Services and Requirements

7.1 Services for Describing AIPs

Many of the considerations and aspects above can be satisfied by providing a mechanism for archives to describe the content and format of their AIPs when they are externalised and exchanged. In OAIS the ability to do this is provided by OAIS 'Packaging Information'. OAIS defines Packaging Information as "The information that describes how the components of an Information Package are logically or physically bound together and how to identify and extract the components.". Packaging Information can be considered as an inventory of the contents of a package that describes what each component of the package contains (e.g. data objects, representation information, preservation description information etc.) and how the components relate to each other (e.g. which checksums, identifiers and provenance events relate to which data files etc.).

The Packaging Information in OAIS does not contain the contents of the package, for example it does not contain the data objects in the package nor the descriptive metadata that captures the semantics of those data objects, but rather the Packaging Information contains pointers and references to where those data objects and metadata are located within the package. When an AIP is internal to an archive these locations could be files on a server and metadata in a database. When AIPs are serialised and externalised, the locations could be files in a directory structure and metadata in a METS file. The important thing is that the Packaging Information can describe and reference the wide range of ways in which data and metadata is held in systems or serialised for exchange.

For example, one approach to implementing Packaging Information when an AIP is exchanged between TDAs or preservation systems would be in the form of a file that can be added to an AIP, or provided alongside an AIP as a sidecar file to describe the contents of the AIP. 'Describe the contents' in this context means how the AIP is structured, the standards and specifications that are being followed, and exactly where inside the AIP to find the requisite parts of the AIP as defined by the OAIS Information Model. For example, this would enable an archive to say that a given package is a Bagit bag that follows OCFL, it contains versions 1,2 of the AIP, and that metadata file X within directory Y contains the semantic description of the contents of the AIP and is in JSON format and follows DataCite etc.

The ability to add Packaging Information to existing AIPs either by injecting it into the AIP or by providing it as separate description such as a sidecar file means that Packaging Information can be added to / layered upon whatever data structures, packaging formats, metadata standards and syntax etc. are already in use. This meets the requirement of EDEN not constraining TDAs in their use of appropriate standards and specifications for their content.

AIPs and related AIP services should follow the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF). For example, AIPs should have identifiers (which will typically be distinct from the identifiers of the research objects they may contain), they should follow open and well defined specifications (e.g. the OAIS Information Model) and they should be both human and machine readable. This need to follow the EOSC IF creates further requirements for EDEN AIP services.

The use of OAIS Packaging Information to describe the contents of an AIP leads to the need for two services, one for AIP semantic Packaging Information and one for AIP technical Packaging Information. These services are described below.

Service	EOSC Interoperability Framework Level	Description
AIP Semantic Packaging Information Service	Semantic	The service allows a TDA to describe the contents of an AIP by providing OAIS Packaging Information for the AIP. The packaging information shall be able to describe the formats, schemas, vocabularies, standards and specifications that are used for all components of the AIP in order to ensure the semantics of each component are well defined.
AIP Technical Packaging Information Service	Technical	The service allows a TDA to describe the contents of an AIP by providing OAIS Packaging Information that describes the technical details of the AIP. This allows external entities to understand both the contents of the AIP and what standards and specifications are being used for the serialisation and exchange of the AIP.

Table 7.1.1: AIP Services for Packaging Information

The requirements that these services should satisfy are listed below.

Service	Requirement ID	Requirement Description
AIP Semantic Packaging Information Service	INTEROPERABILITY-SEMANTIC-REQ-031	The OAIS Packaging Information for an AIP should reference a publicly accessible and machine readable description of the OAIS Information Model so that the OAIS semantics of the Packaging Information are well defined.
AIP Semantic Packaging Information Service	INTEROPERABILITY-SEMANTIC-REQ-023	The OAIS Packaging Information has the ability to describe the formats, schemas, vocabularies, standards and specifications used for all components of the AIP.
AIP Semantic Packaging Information Service	INTEROPERABILITY-SEMANTIC-REQ-032	The OAIS Packaging Information for an AIP supports referencing of publicly accessible schemas and semantics used for each component of the OAIS Information Model that is implemented in a given AIP.
AIP Technical Packaging Information Service	INTEROPERABILITY-TECHNICAL-REQ-027	An AIP should have a persistent and unique identifier that is held in the OAIS Packaging Information and can be used to unambiguously reference the AIP.
AIP Technical Packaging Information Service	INTEROPERABILITY-TECHNICAL-REQ-029	The OAIS Packaging Information for an AIP should be human and machine readable

Information Service		
AIP Technical Packaging Information Service	INTEROPERABILITY-TECHNICAL-REQ-022	The OAIS Packaging Information for an AIP should be flexible so it can accommodate the wide range of standards, specifications and implementation choices that archives and repositories use when they describe, store and manage their AIPs.
AIP Technical Packaging Information Service	INTEROPERABILITY-TECHNICAL-REQ-024	The OAIS Packaging Information for an AIP should support the evolution of AIP contents over time, including support for AIP versioning and determining or describing the deltas between AIP versions.
AIP Technical Packaging Information Service	INTEROPERABILITY-TECHNICAL-REQ-025	The OAIS Packaging Information for an AIP Packaging can be added to, or provided alongside, the existing packaging mechanisms used by a TDA or preservation system.
AIP Technical Packaging Information Service	INTEROPERABILITY-TECHNICAL-REQ-026	OAIS Packaging Information for an AIP should be able to describe and reference the physical location of data and metadata within the AIP. It should be able to reference the contents of the AIP when held internally within an archive or when the AIP is serialised and externalised for exchange. Referencing includes the ability to reference files, parts of files (e.g. metadata elements within an XML files), information in a database, or resolvable identifiers that reference external systems.
AIP Technical Packaging Information Service	INTEROPERABILITY-TECHNICAL-REQ-053	The OAIS Packaging Information for an AIP has a referencing mechanism, e.g. URIs and JSON-LD, that allows it to reference external schemas, vocabularies, ontologies, standards etc. that are used by each of the components of the AIP.
AIP Technical Packaging Information Service	INTEROPERABILITY-TECHNICAL-REQ-028	AIP identifiers should follow a recognised and public PID scheme.

Table 7.1.2: Requirements for the AIP Packaging Information Services

7.2 Services for Validating AIPs

The ability to fully describe the contents of an AIP in terms of the OAIS information model enables individual AIPs to be assessed for their level of conformance.

For AIPs to conform to OAIS, several requirements must be satisfied. OAIS conformance is defined in Section 1.4 (OAIS M3): "A conforming OAIS Archive implementation shall support, and be able to map to the

components of, the model of information described in 2.3 and 4.3. The OAIS Reference Model does not define or require any particular method of implementation of these concepts.". Sections 2.3 and 4.3 of the OAIS specification are the OAIS Information Model. Some parts of the OAIS information model are mandatory for all package types (SIPs,AIPs,DIPs), for example a package must contain the minimum Representation Information needed for a Designated Community to understand the contents of the package. Some parts of the OAIS model are mandatory only for AIPs, for example all parts of PDI MUST be provided for an AIP but are not necessary for SIPs and DIPs.

An OAIS AIP must satisfy two things:

1. The AIP must include all mandatory parts of the OAIS Information Model.
2. There must be a mapping of the contents of an AIP to the OAIS Information Model.

As described earlier, this can be satisfied by providing Packaging Information as described by OAIS. If an AIP is serialised so it can be exchanged with another OAIS, then the AIP serialisation must include Packaging Information which describes where to find each part of the OAIS information model in the serialised AIP (e.g. in which metadata / data files).

In the context of EDEN, for AIPs to be demonstrably conformant to the OAIS Information Model:

- The AIPs must include Packaging Information
- The Packaging Information must follow the OAIS Information Model
- The AIP must include all mandatory parts of the OAIS Information Model and these must be listed in the Packaging Information

It is important to note that EDEN is NOT mandating that all AIPs must be OAIS conformant (in reality this won't always be possible either initially or over the long term), rather EDEN is specifying that should a TDA wish to demonstrate OAIS AIP conformance then meeting the requirements above will be necessary for it to do so.

In addition to conformance to the OAIS model, a third-party receiving an AIP may wish to confirm that the TDA providing the AIP has the rights to do so and has the ability to grant the rights required by the receiving party for processing the AIP contents, for example so they can be stored or undergo preservation actions. This requires the ability to check the rights associated with the AIP, i.e. validate that they are sufficient to cover the purpose for which the AIP is being externalised or exchanged.

Collectively, this leads to services that can be used for validation testing.

Service	EOSC Interoperability Framework Level	Description
AIP OAIS Semantic Validation Service	Semantic	The Packaging Information for an AIP is evaluated against the components of the OAIS Information Model to determine the extent to which some or all of the required components of OAIS are present in the AIP. This allows the level of OAIS conformance to be assessed according to the semantics of the OAIS Information Model.
AIP OAIS Technical Validation Service	Technical	The OAIS Packaging Information for an AIP is tested to validate the AIP contents at a technical level. This includes validation of the Packaging Information against a schema in order to check that it is syntactically valid, i.e. well-formed, and testing of the contents of the AIP to confirm they are present and correct as listed in the Packaging Information.

AIP Rights Validation Service	Legal	The TDA can check the rights statements in an AIP to confirm that it has a valid legal basis for holding the AIP, performing preservation actions on it, and/or transferring it to other TDA or using third-party preservation services.
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Table 7.2.1: Services for Validating AIPs

The requirements that these services should satisfy are listed below.

Service	Requirement ID	Requirement Description
AIP OAIS Semantic Validation Service	INTEROPERABILITY-SEMANTIC-REQ-033	The OAIS Packaging Information for an AIP should reference a publicly accessible and machine readable description of the OAIS Information Model so that the contents of the AIP can be assessed for conformance to the OAIS Information Model.
AIP OAIS Technical Validation Service	INTEROPERABILITY-TECHNICAL-REQ-030	The OAIS Packaging Information for an AIP should be in a machine readable format, e.g. JSON, and a schema shall be available for validation, e.g. JSON schema
AIP OAIS Technical Validation Service	INTEROPERABILITY-TECHNICAL-REQ-021	The OAIS Packaging Information references the contents of the AIP, e.g. the location within the AIP each component of the OAIS Information Model. These references, i.e. pointers, are evaluated to check that they resolve correctly to the components of the AIP.
AIP OAIS Technical Validation Service	INTEROPERABILITY-TECHNICAL-REQ-054	The contents of the AIP are validated for conformance to the formats and schemas listed in the OAIS AIP Packaging Information. For example, is metadata in the AIP in syntactically valid JSON, XML, CSV etc. and does it conform to corresponding schemas (JSON schemas, XML schemas) where used. If the AIP is in some form of container, e.g. Bagit then this is also validated.
AIP Rights Validation Service	INTEROPERABILITY-LEGAL-REQ-033	The Packaging Information for an AIP should support inclusion of rights information relevant for the digital preservation of the AIP contents. The rights statements should be in a machine readable format to allow for automated analysis.

Table 7.2.2: Requirements for AIP Validation Services

7.3 Services for Exchanging AIPs

Once AIPs are described using OAIS Packaging Information then they can be exchanged with external entities such as other TDAs or external preservation services in the knowledge that the receiving party will have the information needed to be able to interpret and process the contents of the AIP.

This leads to the need for an AIP exchange service

Service	EOSC Interoperability Framework Level	Description
AIP Exchange Service	Technical	It should be possible to request and transfer an AIP from one location to another, e.g. between TDAs. The service that supports AIP exchange should support incremental and full transfers (e.g. transfer of a whole AIP in one shot for small AIPs or transfer in batches of files for large AIPs).

Table 7.3.1: AIP Exchange Service

The requirements that this service should satisfy are listed below.

Service	Requirement ID	Requirement Description
AIP Exchange Service	INTEROPERABILITY-TECHNICAL-REQ-055	There is a defined protocol and API endpoints for (a) requesting AIP information for an AIP, i.e. OAIS Packaging Information, (b) requesting part or all of the contents of an AIP, and (c) transferring the requested contents either in one pass or incrementally in stages if the AIP is large.
AIP Exchange Service	INTEROPERABILITY-TECHNICAL-REQ-056	The AIP exchange service allows for the request and transfer of both (a) the complete contents of an AIP of a specified version, and (b) the deltas between AIPs of two different specified versions. For example, this allows two organisations to synchronise the copies of an AIP without needing to transfer the full AIP each time an update is made.

Table 7.3.2: Requirements for AIP Exchange Service

7.4 Services for AIP Cross-walks and Transformations

The need to accommodate a wide range of formats, standards and specifications that are used for AIP contents will inevitably require services that can be used to convert AIP components between various formats and specifications. This includes metadata cross-walks and package transformations such as repacking using a different structure or container. There are other services in EDEN that provide this functionality. Although they are important services in EDEN and they are necessary for use of the AIP services described in this report, they are not AIP specific and hence they are not discussed further here.

7.5 Detailed Requirements Analysis

A detailed analysis of the expressiveness of the OAIS Information Model for AIPs and whether it is able to accommodate the wide range of AIP content types that need to be supported is provided in Appendix A.

Considerable time and effort could be spent creating a comprehensive set of requirements for an EDEN AIP specification, for example listing every type of information that needs to be stored in an AIP plus listing every preservation process that can result in artefacts that also need to be stored in an AIP.

However, given the work that has already gone into existing AIP specifications, for example E-ARK and the OAIS Reference Model, existing specifications (e.g. OAIS RM and OAIS IF, E-ARK) are likely to already be sufficient. Furthermore, EDEN should re-use and build upon existing standards where possible and avoid re-inventing the wheel. Therefore, the approach we have taken to detailed requirements analysis for EDEN AIPs

is to determine whether existing standards can be reused for EDEN, either as-is or with further extensions, rather than to specify EDEN AIPs from scratch. The requirements analysis processes is as follows:

1. Identify a set of requirement sources that cover the majority of EDEN needs and use cases.
2. Compare these requirements with existing standards to identify if these standards are already sufficient for EDEN's needs.
3. Start with the OAIS Information Model as the defacto standard for organising the information in an AIP.
4. Identify any gaps in the OAIS Information Model and any additional specifications that are required.

The sources of requirements that have been analysed are listed below.

Requirement Source	Analysis Performed
Core Preservation Processes (CPP)	Can the OAIS Information Model support all the artefacts of the preservation process, for example the data and metadata inputs and outputs, and the provenance information and other documentation that records what was done? AIPs need to have the ability to store a wide range of artefacts from CPPs such as checksums, file format information, significant properties, descriptive metadata, rights information etc.
Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix (TTRAM) [R23]	Some, but not all, of the functions/activities in TTRAM will generate information that will need to be retained in AIPs. Therefore, an analysis is needed of the information requirements of TTRAM processes. The information requirements that arise from TRAM are cross-checked with the OAIS Information Model.
F-UJI Assessment Metrics for FAIR data	AIPs should contain all the information that is needed to be able to understand and use the data within them. This means AIPs need to be able to hold information needed for data to be FAIR. One way to extract requirements for this is to analyse the F-UJI FAIR assessment metrics [R24], which uses the FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics . [R25] Note that it is not a requirement for a system that stores, manages or provides access to AIPs to itself support all the FAIR metrics. Rather the contents of the AIP must contain everything needed to allow the contents of the AIP to be provided in a FAIR way (which would usually be done through conversion into DIPs).
CoreTrustSeal [R28]	CoreTrustSeal is one of the foundational standards that is recommended by the EOSC TF on LTDP. AIPs need to be able to hold the information needed for Digital Object Management in CoreTrustSeal.
EOSC TF on LTDP [R26]	Support for the recommendations of the EOSC Task Force on Long Term Digital Preservation, for example that “@Digital objects should include metadata that specify their level of care and the timeframes or criteria for reappraisal of the level of care”.
EOSC Interoperability Framework [R27]	The ability to exchange AIPs between TDAs and preservation services in EOSC requires that AIPs conform to the interoperability principles and requirements of EOSC IF. This includes the need to support technical, semantic and legal interoperability.

EDEN Pillars of Fitness and Reuse	AIPs should contain the information needed to support the assessment of Fitness and the Pillars of Reuse, which includes contextual quality, technical quality and metadata quality. Quality and fitness has been identified by EDEN as a 'blindspot' for digital preservation (there is typically too much focus on purely the technical side) and therefore it is essential that EDEN AIPs are able to include the information needed when removing this blindspot.
EDEN WP3	AIPs need to be capable of storing the domain and discipline specific information needed to support the needs of Designated Communities, for example as surveyed by WP3 and documented in D3.1. This includes the ability to accommodate the wide range of metadata and data types.
Digital Preservation Supply Chains	Support for the exchange and use of AIP content in supply chains, for example if a TDA decides to use external services or systems for performing LTDP. This recognises the increasingly 'supply chain' nature of the software, systems, people and services that sit behind a TDA and enables it to fulfil its mission.

Table 7.5.1: Requirement Sources

A detailed analysis is provided in Appendix A. The conclusions of this analysis are below:

- The information identified as needing inclusion in EDEN AIPs can be described by the OAIS Information Model.
- There does not appear to be significant gaps in the OAIS model that prevent it being used to describe the contents of an EDEN AIP.
- All parts of the OAIS Information Model are needed in order to support the types of information that need to be stored in EDEN AIPs.
- There does not appear to be opportunities for reducing the OAIS Information Model, for example creating a simplified 'OAIS Lite' version. The full OAIS Information model is both sufficient and necessary.
- Some information requirements from EDEN span multiple components of the OAIS Information Model. For example, support for FAIR metrics and support for Quality information both cover multiple parts of the OAIS Information Model including both OAIS PDI and OAIS Representation Information. Therefore, there will sometimes be an n:m type mapping between OAIS concepts and the types of information that need to be retained in EDEN AIPs.

The above means that the OAIS Information Model for AIPs can be used form the basis of Packaging Information for EDEN AIPs and in turn this can enable EDEN AIPs to be evaluated for OAIS conformance.

7.6 Summary of AIP Services

The focus in EDEN is on AIP services for interoperability and exchange. The proposed approach of using OAIS Packaging Information to describe the contents of an AIP according to the OAIS Information Model leads to the need for services for both describing packages and validating the contents of such packages. When an AIP has been serialised, described using OAIS Packaging Information and validated, then it is ready for exchange. This requires an exchange service. Many additional services will be required within a TDA for constructing, storing, managing and preserving AIPs. These are out of scope because they are 'internal' services.

It is also important to re-iterate that EDEN does not mandate that the EDEN AIP specification is used within an TDA as part of its day to day operations. That isn't to say that a TDA shouldn't use the EDEN AIP specification internally if it wants to and indeed it may be beneficial to do so, for example to help confirm that it does indeed have the information it needs in its AIPs in order to fulfil its remit.

The main purpose of the EDEN AIP specification is for use at the point at which the TDA needs to demonstrate OAIS conformance and exchange content with external parties. This could be when exchanging AIPs with another TDA or a LTDP service; it could be when demonstrating to assessment and certification bodies that the TDA holds the necessary information in their AIPs to fulfil their duties; or it could be when the TDA is asked to demonstrate transparency and good practice to Producers or Consumers.

The set of services proposed in this section can be chained together to support an AIP exchange workflow. An example is shown below.

Figure 7.1: Example of how EDEN AIP Services can be combined

The workflow below describes the example in the diagram where two TDAs (A,B) want to exchange an AIP (from A->B).

1. TDA A has its own internal structure and services for describing and storing its AIPs (e.g. files on a server, metadata in a database, internal schemas and formats etc).
2. An AIP is exported and converted into a serialised format (e.g. metadata in JSON, XML etc., files in folders etc). This could include following specs like RO-Crate, Bagit, E-ARK, OCFL etc. etc. This involves the use of the metadata crosswalk and package transformation services to get the AIP into an appropriate format. These services are covered elsewhere in D2.1.
3. The OAIS AIP Packaging Information services are then used to generate OAIS Packaging Information for the AIP. This is a mapping of the AIP contents to the OAIS Information Model plus a description of how the package is structured and the various standards and specifications that are used within the package.
4. The OAIS Packing Information is used by a set of Validation Services (Semantic, Technical, Legal) to check whether the contents of the package is complete, correct, conforms to OAIS, contains necessary rights etc. The level of conformance and any gaps etc. are provided as a validation report.

The TDA may at this point find that there are things missing and it may go back and revise the way the AIP content is exported/cross-walked/transformed etc.

5. The AIP is ready for exchange and is transferred from TDA A to TDA B using the AIP Exchange Service
6. The receiving TDA then reverses the process. The TDA validates what it receives by running the validation services on its side. The TDA uses its own set of cross-walks and transformations to convert the AIP into whatever format it needs so that it can ingest and process the AIP. The AIP is then ingested and is held in whatever internal representation TDA chooses to use.

8 Outlook and Next Steps

Having identified a set of EDEN services for AIP interoperability and exchange, the next step will be to develop a set of corresponding service specifications that can be used as the starting point for implementation work.

The AIP services identified in this report centre on the use of OAIS Packaging Information. Therefore, at the core of the specification of AIP services in EDEN is the need for a specification of an OAIS Packaging Information format. At the time of writing, this specification is under development.

Initial analysis suggests that the EDEN AIP Packaging Information format should be achievable using a combination of JSON, JSON schema, JSON linked data, JSON path and XPath. The next step will be to design and implement the Packaging Information model in more detail, for example using [LinkML](#). A key capability of Packaging Information in EDEN is the ability to reference external schemas in order to establish shared and machine-readable semantics. This referencing mechanism can be achieved using linked data, e.g. JSON-LD. Crucially this can be used to point to defined semantics not only for the contents of the AIP (e.g. dataset semantics defined by DCAT-AP) but also to the semantics of the OAIS Information Model itself. This means that producing and publishing a machine-readable description of the OAIS Information Model for AIPs will also be necessary.

As described earlier in this report, work is currently in progress with the CCSDS MOIMS-DAI group to define the OAIS Interoperability Framework, including a JSON schema for the OAIS Information Model. This is relevant to the work that needs to be done next in EDEN and the project will look for opportunities to collaborate with the OAIS IF team.

The acid test for new specifications and services is to demonstrate in practice that they function as intended and can be implemented in an unambiguous way. A common approach in these situations is to provide a reference implementation. Therefore, one of the next steps will be to identify a subset of standards currently in use (E-ARK, RO-Crate, OCFL and Bagit are examples) and show how OAIS Packaging Information can be used to describe an information package that is implemented using one or more of these standards.

A further acid test is that it should be possible to use AIPs for lossless exchange of content between TDAs / LTDP systems, or that externalised AIPs can be successfully used to support Business Continuity and Disaster Recovery (BCDR). Both can be tested through a 'roundtrip test' that uses a serialisation format for an AIP and tests that the AIP contains all the required components of the AIP information model along with the data being preserved.

For example, a simple roundtrip test would be to demonstrate the following process (using a test system):

1. Serialise and export an AIP from an archive or LTDP system.
2. Store the AIP externally.
3. Delete the AIP from the archive.
4. Re-ingest the contents of the AIP into the archive.
5. Confirm that the system is restored to its original state, i.e. there is no loss of information or data.

A similar test can be done when exchanging content between archives:

1. Serialise and export an AIP from archive A.
2. Transfer the AIP to archive B.
3. Ingest the contents of the AIP into archive B.
4. Confirm that the same information and data is available in both systems, i.e. there is no loss of information or data during the exchange.

Ideally, it should be possible to cycle AIPs back and forth between different archives and LTDP services with no loss. Exchange between archives helps to confirm that: (a) the AIP format successfully contains all the necessary information to support 'lossless' transfer, and (b) the specification of the AIP is unambiguous and isn't interpreted differently by different archives/systems/vendors. The examples above can also be readily extended to cover scenarios where partial AIPs are exchanged, e.g. the deltas between two versions, for example when synchronising the content held in two TDAs or systems. Again the objective is to show that this is a lossless process.

Finally, it is likely that the EDEN AIP services, their requirements and specifications, and their implementation will all need to evolve as the EDEN project progresses. Therefore, this report should be considered as an initial version of work that is very much in progress and not as a definitive statement of what will be built in EDEN.

9 Acknowledgements

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- EDEN WP1 and WP2 partners for their suggestions and advice, for example how SIPs, AIPs and DIPs are implemented in practice within working TDAs.

The contents of this report are the findings of the author. No endorsement is implied from any of the above. However, discussions and opinions of the people listed above have been very useful in coming to the conclusions described in this report.

10 References

No	Description/ Link
R1	REFERENCE MODEL FOR AN OPEN ARCHIVAL INFORMATION SYSTEM (OAIS) RECOMMENDED PRACTICE CCSDS 650.0-M-3 MAGENTA BOOK December 2024 https://ccsds.org/wp-content/uploads/gravity_forms/5-448e85c647331d9cbaf66c096458bdd5/2025/01/650x0m3.pdf
R2	Digital Preservation Coalition Rapid Assessment Model (DPC RAM) https://www.dpconline.org/digipres/implement-digipres/dpc-ram
R3	CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2022). CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025 (V01.00). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051012
R4	The National Digital Stewardship Alliance Levels of Digital Preservation https://ndsa.org/publications/levels-of-digital-preservation/
R5	Kearney, Mike & Giaretta, David & Garrett, John & Hughes, Steven. (2023). New Standards for Archive and Information Interoperability: A Digital Preservation Perspective. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/387723314_New_Standards_for_Archive_and_Information_Interoperability_A_Digital_Preservation_Perspective
R6	David Giaretta's github repo for OAIS IF https://github.com/dgiaretta/OAISIF
R7	Digital Information LifeCycle Interoperability Standards Board (DILCIS Board) E-ARK specifications https://dilcis.eu/specifications
R8	XML FORMATTED DATA UNIT (XFDU) STRUCTURE AND CONSTRUCTION RULES RECOMMENDED STANDARD CCSDS 661.0-B-1 BLUE BOOK September 2008 https://ccsds.org/Pubs/661x0b1.pdf
R9	Jefferies, N., Metz, R., Morley, J., Warner, S., & Woods, A. (2024). Oxford Common File Layout - Specification (1.1.1). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14204936
R10	The Moab Design for Digital Object Versioning Richard N Anderson Digital Library Systems and Services Stanford University Libraries 15 July 2013 https://stacks.stanford.edu/file/druid:vt105qd7230/The%20Moab%20Design%20for%20Digital%20Object%20Versioning%202013-07-15.pdf
R11	Stian Soiland-Reyes, Peter Sefton, Mercè Crosas, Leyla Jael Castro, Frederik Coppens, José M. Fernández, Daniel Garijo, Björn Grüning, Marco La Rosa, Simone Leo, Eoghan Ó Carragáin, Marc Portier, Ana Trisovic, RO-Crate Community, Paul Groth, Carole Goble (2022): Packaging research artefacts with RO-Crate. Data Science 5(2) https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-210053
R12	Portland Common Data Model (PCDM) https://github.com/duraspace/pcdm/wiki
R13	Chard, K., D'Arcy, M., Heavner, B., Foster, I., Kesselman, C., Madduri, R., Rodriguez, A., Soiland-Reyes, S., Goble, C., Clark, K., Deutsch, E. W., Dinov, I., Price, N., & Toga, A. (2016). I'll take that to go: Big data bags and minimal identifiers for exchange of large, complex datasets. 2016 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (big Data), 319–328. https://doi.org/10.1109/BigData.2016.7840618
R14	Kunze, J., Littman, J., Madden, E., Scancella, J., and C. Adams, "The BagIt File Packaging Format (V1.0)", RFC 8493, DOI 10.17487/RFC8493, October 2018 https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc8493
R15	Ivonne, A., Christophe, B., Daan, B., Maggie, H., Sharif, I., Thomas, J., Larry, L., Karsten, P.-. von G., Robert, Q., Alexander, S., Ulrich, S., Stian, S.-R., George, S., Dieter, . van U., Claus, W., Peter, W., & Carlo, Z. (2023). FAIR Digital Object Technical Overview. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7824714
R16	FAIR Digital Object Framework Documentation, Working Draft, 27 October 2022.

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R17	Rampin et al, (2016), ReproZip: The Reproducibility Packer, Journal of Open Source Software, 1(8), 107, doi:10.21105/joss.00107 https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.00107
R18	Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard (METS) https://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/
R19	PREMIS Preservation Metadata Maintenance Activity https://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/
R20	Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) - Version 3 W3C Recommendation 22 August 2024 https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/
R21	DDI Alliance https://ddialliance.org/
R22	DataCite https://datacite.org/
R23	L'Hours, H., Kleemola, M., Parkes, O., Recker, J., Duvaud, S., van Horik, R., Alaterä, T. J., Liberante, F., Conzett, P., Kaartinen, H., Bäckman, S., & Esteves, E. (2025). FIDELIS TTRAMatrix Design Statement. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15677076
R24	Anusuriya Devaraju, & Robert Huber. (2020). F-UJI - An Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6361400
R25	Huber, R. (2025). FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics (0.8). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045911
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R30	Lots Of Copies Keep Stuff Safe. https://www.lockss.org/
R31	EOSC EDEN Deliverable D2.1 Specifications and Architecture (Iteration 1) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17232536

Appendix A

Requirement Sources

The table below covers sources of requirements from EDEN / FIDELIS and external sources. Each source has been analysed for corresponding AIP requirements. For example, this included analysing EDEN Core Preservation Processes (CPPs) for artefacts (inputs, outputs, provenance records) that need to be captured in an AIP.

What	Analysis Performed	Outcome	References
EDEN Core Preservation Processes (CPP)	Detailed comparison of CPPs with the OAIS Information Model for AIPs.	OAIS Information Model is sufficient. See separate section below for the analysis.	EDEN CPPs
FIDELIS TTRAM (Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix)	Detailed comparison of the TTRAM matrix with the OAIS Information Model for AIPs.	OAIS Information Model is sufficient. See separate section below for the analysis.	FIDELIS TTRAM
F-UJI Assessment Metrics for FAIR data	Detailed comparison of the F-UJI metrics with the OAIS Information Model for AIPs. See separate section below for the analysis.	OAIS Information Model is sufficient. See separate section below for the analysis.	F-UJI Assessment Metrics for FAIR data
RDA WG TRSP (trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers)	The RDA TRSP working group has identified a set of attributes for repositories. High level categories follow TRUST, e.g. Transparency, Sustainability, Responsibility, Technology etc. Within each area are specific attributes, e.g. Responsibility → Schema → Metadata and Data, Responsibility → Stewardship → Integrity. These were reviewed in terms of (a) would corresponding information be held in AIPs and (b) is the OAIS Information Model flexible enough to accommodate such information.	OAIS Information Model is sufficient.	RDA WG TRSP
EDEN Domain Specific Requirements in D3.1	WP3 in EDEN has analysed the discipline specific requirements and needs of the project. The survey done in WP3 and documented in D3.1 highlights the diversity of standards and formats used, for example for the range of metadata schemas and file formats in use.	EDEN AIPs need to be very flexible in the data and metadata schemas that can be used for the contents of an AIP. EDEN should not impose or mandate specific schemas. This is especially true for Representation Information in OAIS (semantic and structural) as well as the file formats used for Digital Objects.	EDEN Deliverable D3.1 Report on discipline requirements and needs

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

<p>Recommendations of the EOSC Task Force on LTDP</p>	<p>The EOSC Task Force on Long Term Data Preservation (EOSC TF LTDP) has made a series of recommendations for how LTDP should be achieved in EOSC, for example to ensure data remains FAIR over Time. Some of the relevant recommendations are below.</p> <p>19. @Repositories should specify all the levels of care they apply to objects within their collection, including through repository and digital object registry metadata</p> <p>20. @Digital objects should include metadata that specify their level of care and th timeframes or criteria for reappraisal of the level of care*</p> <p>24. @FAIR-enabling practices undertaken by repositories should be made transparent to users and funders to increase trust in services*</p> <p>53. @Digital Objects and the services that enable their FAIRness, deposit, storage curation, access and preservation should be supported in transparent efforts to use assessment as a route to assistance and improvement*.</p> <p>54. @Efforts by repositories and other data services to share transparent information about their functions, activities and objects should be rewarded by targeted investment for improvement*.</p> <p>55. @No repository or digital object should be unnecessarily excluded from any part of EOSC</p>	<p>EOSC TF LTDP recommendations can be supported through EDEN AIPs, for example by ensuring AIPs contain information that supports:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence (e.g. provenance metadata) that supports assessment of how a repository is managing its digital objects. • Metadata that supports the specification of levels of care for digital content, including reappraisal over time. • Metadata that supports transparency and the FAIR principles. • Inclusivity, i.e. the flexibility for repositories to use whatever specifications and standards are most appropriate for them and not be excluded from EOSC because they don't follow a prescribed model for their AIPs. <p>The specific way in which some of the recommendations from the EOSC TF on LTDP should be implemented and achieved is not yet clear, especially in the area of quality assessment and levels of care. This is an area that EDEN will be working on. Therefore, the requirement on AIPs is that they should be flexible in the standards and specifications that can be used within them, which will allow them to accommodate the appropriate models of quality and care as and when they are developed.</p>	<p>LTDP-TF Recommendations & Assertions</p>
<p>Core Trust Seal</p>	<p>CoreTrustSeal is recommended by the EOSC TF on LTDP as the basis for TDRs in EOSC. Therefore, it makes sense to ensure that EDEN AIPs support the digital preservation aspects of CTS, for example under CTS Digital Object Management.</p> <p>CoreTrustSeal, including the Extended Guidance, was reviewed to identify any areas of information that may need to be held in AIPs that are not already covered by the analysis of EDEN CPPs, TTRAM attributes, F-UJI, D3.1 etc.</p>	<p>OAIS Information Model is sufficient.</p>	<p>CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025</p>
<p>File Format Registries</p>	<p>There are multiple file format identification tools and registries, for example DROID as a tool for identifying file formats according to the PRONOM registry and Apache Tika as a tool for identifying file formats according to the IANA Media Types registry (formally known as MIME types). File format identification is a core part of digital preservation and the tools used and the results achieved should be recorded in AIPs as part of provenance information. This is covered further by CPP-008. OAIS PDI allows this information to be captured in AIPs.</p>	<p>OAIS Information Model is sufficient.</p>	<p>DigiPres Workbench</p>

Requirements from EDEN CPP

The [Core Preservation Processes](#) work in EDEN WP1 T1.2 can be used to derive requirements on the information that needs to be stored in AIPs.

It is useful to cross-check the CPP work in WP1 with the EDEN AIP requirements to make sure that (a) the AIP specification can accommodate all the artefacts created by CPP processes, and (b) the use of the OAIS Information Model as the basis for an EDEN AIP doesn't have any gaps or limitations, i.e. the OAIS information model is sufficiently flexible and complete.

CPP Version: 1.0 29 Aug 2025

CPP ID	CPP Title	CPP Description	AIP Requirement	Support in the OAIS Information Model
CPP-001	Checksums Generation and Reporting	The TDA records checksums for every file.	AIP MUST be able to store one or more checksums for each file in the AIP.	PDI: Fixity Information
CPP-002	Checksum Validation	The TDA validates checksums against those stored in the Information Package at Ingest or Access.	AIP MUST be able to record when checksum validation has taken place, who by, for what reason and the outcome	PDI: Fixity Information PDI: Provenance Information
CPP-003	Integrity Checking	The TDA supports periodic integrity checking, reporting any damaged or missing files.	AIP MUST be able to record results of periodic integrity checks, including any files that have failed the check and are missing or damaged.	PDI: Fixity Information PDI: Provenance Information
CPP-004	Data Corruption Management	The TDA replaces damaged files from replicated copies and report on actions taken.	AIP MUST be able to record if any content in the AIP remains lost or corrupted following repair operations. The AIP SHOULD be able to record if further repair operations are possible or are pending.	PDI: Fixity Information PDI: Provenance Information
CPP-005	Identifier Management	Identifiers are assigned to objects, information packages and/or metadata, and managed according to their lifecycle.	AIP MUST be able to hold PIDs for the contents of the AIP. This could be per file, per Data Object, per Information Object etc.	PDI: Reference Information
CPP-006	AIP Batch Export	As part of an exit strategy, the TDA batch exports information packages and all associated metadata in a manageable format/structure for	It SHOULD be possible to use AIPs as part of an exit strategy. It SHOULD be possible to batch/bulk export AIP content from a LTDP system.	Representation Information. Representation Information Network

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

		ingest into another TDA.	The AIP SHOULD include all metadata relevant to the digital content. The AIP SHOULD be in a format that allows ingest into other systems.	PDI
CPP-007	Virus Scanning	Information packages are virus checked, with appropriate facilities for quarantine.	AIPs SHOULD be able to hold records of virus scanning and the results. This includes recording if viruses have been detected, if viruses have been removed, and if viruses are still present.	PDI: Provenance Information
CPP-008	File Format Identification	The TDA identifies file formats to the appropriate level of precision, based on an existing registry (IANA MIME types, PRONOM, etc.).	AIPs MUST be able to hold file format identification information for the files in the AIP. The information should include the identified file format(s), the schema(s) used (e.g. PRONOM), and any associated information such as confidence levels and tools used.	PDI: Reference Information (e.g. PRONOM IDs) PDI: Provenance Information (e.g. file format identification process and tools) Representation Information (e.g. file format specifications).
CPP-009	Metadata Extraction	The TDA extracts characteristics (such as size, image dimensions, video codec, audio run time, creating application).	AIPs MUST be able to hold technical characteristics for the digital content (files, objects) in the AIP.	Representation Information. PDI: Context Information (e.g. what external software or environments can render/process the data).
CPP-010	File Format Validation	The TDA validates files against file format specifications.	The AIP SHOULD be able to record the outcome of file format validation including which files have been validated, using which tools, when and with what results.	PDI: Provenance Information
CPP-011	Replication	The TDA automatically manages the replication of Information Packages to multiple storage locations (potentially in different geographical locations).	An AIP does not need to record all the locations where its contents are being stored. An AIP MAY include a reference to an external system which contains information about the storage of the AIP	PDI: context Information (e.g. what external database holds information on where the AIP is stored). This allows the AIP to be linked to Data Management Information (see OAIS 4.3.4), which is 'outside' of the AIP.
CPP-012	Risk Mitigation	The TDA enables the design, development, and management of plans for mitigating identified preservation risks.	An AIP SHOULD be able to hold the preservation plan for the content of the AIP, for example, the plan for file format migration and when it has been done, or will be done. Plans could be per file, per Data Object, or per Information Object. An AIP SHOULD be able to hold information on the risk assessment of its contents, e.g. assessment of file format obsolescence, including the criteria	OAIS has lots to say about preservation planning as part of the functional model, but very little to say about where preservation plans are held, e.g. as part of an AIP. OAIS Data Management Information (see OAIS 4.3.4) is an option, but this is 'outside' of the AIP. For the contents of the AIP:

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

			that have been applied and the results of the assessment. An example is NARA's file format risk assessment, which could be recorded inside the AIP.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> External preservation plans could be referenced using PDI: Context Information. Execution of plans can be recorded in PDI: Provenance Information. Preservation plans for future actions could be included in Representation Information (Other) as a description of what to do in order to interpret the object in the future. PDI: Provenance Information can be used to record the status and execution of preservation plans. PDI: Context Information (e.g. references to external file format registries and risks)
CPP-013	Object Management Reporting	The TDA delivers reporting to enable the effective management of objects. This must include a wide range of functional, operational, and statistical reports and analytics.	It SHOULD be possible to interrogate an AIP to determine its content so that information can be extracted to support reporting.	Package Description (description of the contents of a package that supports finding aids). Representation Information. PDI
CPP-014	File Migration	The TDA supports batch modifications of previously ingested files to prevent a preservation- or access-related risk.	It SHOULD be possible to record that file format migration has been applied to files, including when the migration was done, who by (person or system), using which tools and settings etc. The AIP SHOULD clearly identify which files were the inputs or outputs of migration, i.e. which files have been derived from which other files.	PDI: Provenance Information
CPP-015	Emulation and Rendering Tools	The TDA enables the rendering of objects via the application of emulation and/or other specialist tools.	It SHOULD be possible to record what software applications or emulation environments etc. are needed in order to render the content in the AIP.	PDI: Context Information (e.g. what external software or environments can render/process the data).
CPP-016	Metadata Ingest and Management	The TDA ingests and manages all required metadata including metadata appropriate for specific content types (e.g. geospatial, audio visual).	AIPs MUST be able to store all required metadata for the files in the AIP including metadata that is specific to their content type. It MUST be possible to clearly link metadata in the AIP to files/objects in the AIP.	Representation Information, PDI. Both Representation Information and PDI can be linked to Data Objects (which in turn contain Digital Objects such as files). Therefore, metadata can be linked to files. Furthermore, metadata files are themselves Data

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

				Objects and can have their own representation information and PDI. In this way, rich structures of metadata for domain or discipline specific content can be constructed.
CPP-017	Disposal	The TDA enables the managed disposal of information packages and permits the retention and maintenance of metadata even when the content of the information package has been removed from the TDA.	AIPs MUST be able to store information on retention schedules and disposition of the contents of the AIP. The AIP MUST enable a record to be retained of what content has already been deleted and it MUST allow for retention of metadata that still needs to be kept.	PDI: Provenance Information (e.g. what's been deleted) PDI: Rights Information (e.g. agreements/permissions to retain/delete content) Representation Information (e.g. retained metadata even if the bitstream for a Data Object has been deleted).
CPP-018	Community watch	The TDA monitors its Designated Community in order to identify its evolving needs and knowledge.	The AIP MUST be able to reference knowledge available to the Designated Community that is needed for the contents of the AIP to be interpreted and used.	OAIS has the concept of the Knowledge Base of the Designated Community. This can be referenced from within the AIP, e.g. using PDI Context Information.
CPP-019	Data quality assessment	The TDA evaluates and re-evaluates the data quality of Information Objects.	AIPs MUST be able to store information on the quality of the contents of the AIPs. AIPs SHOULD include information on assessments that have been done (including who, how and why) and the results of these assessments (scores, metrics, issues, conformance with quality reqs, compliance with specifications etc).	PDI: Provenance Information Representation Information
CPP-020	Rights management	The TDA manages rights related to the Information Objects, both for agents inside its scope (access, migrate, etc.) and for end users (access, reuse, etc.)	AIPs MUST be able to store rights information that supports the management and preservation of the contents of the AIP as well as access to and use of the AIP. This includes rights to perform preservation actions, rights to hold or transfer the AIP by a repository, rights to access and use the AIP contents by a designated community.	PDI: Rights Information Also see Annex F of OAIS.
CPP-021	AIP Versioning	The TDA creates successive versions of the Information Objects on its own or on the Producer initiative.	AIPs MUST support transparency and include a full history of the AIP and its contents. It SHOULD be possible to construct a given version of an AIP from its contents, for example by applying deltas between versions to create a complete version of the AIP.	PDI: Provenance Information PDI: Reference Information (e.g. version number of AIP or its contents) PDI: Context Information (e.g. links from one AIP to previous/subsequent versions held elsewhere).

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

				<p>Maybe versions of an AIP can be held as an AIC?</p> <p>Also see OAIS 5.2.4.6 "Distinguishing AIP Versions, AIP Editions and Derived AIPs"</p>
CPP-022	Significant properties definition	The TDA defines significant properties for sets of Information Objects, i.e., properties that it commits to preserve over the long term through preservation actions and rendition.	AIPs MUST include information on the significant properties that need to be preserved.	<p>Information Property, Information Property Description, Transformational Information Property.</p> <p>Note: OAIS defines these terms, but says very little about where they fit in the information model. For example, Information Properties highlight parts of the Representation Information that need to be preserved, but doesn't say how to implement this.</p>
CPP-023	Risk definition and extraction	The TDA monitors technology evolution, identify risks and define detection methods for these risks.	An AIP SHOULD be able to hold information on the risks identified for its contents, for example the results of an assessment of file format obsolescence of the files in the AIP or changes to the knowledge base of the Designated Community that may put the ability to understand and use the contents of the AIP at risk.	PDI: Provenance Information can be used to record the execution and results of risk assessment.
CPP-024	Discovery	The TDA provides catalogue services to its consumers to help them identify objects that they may be interested in.	AIPs SHOULD include information that allows their contents to be catalogued and searched.	<p>Package Description</p> <p>Note: the Package Description in OAIS contains information for use by Access Aids, i.e. it is specifically intended to help the contents of the AIP to be discoverable. This provides information that could be used in an external system for searching.</p>
CPP-025	Access	The TDA gives access to its Information Objects to authorized internal users or end users.	AIPs SHOULD include information that can be used to control access so some/all or the contents is only made available to authorised users.	PDI: Access Rights Information
CPP-026	File Normalisation	The TDA performs operations on the Data Objects prior to ingest in order to comply with its format requirements.	<p>AIPs SHOULD include information on the provenance of the contents of the AIP, including any format conversions that have been applied when data was ingested.</p> <p>If the AIP contains both the original and normalised versions, then the AIP SHOULD identify which is which and the relationship between them, e.g. that File Y is a normalised version of File X.</p>	<p>PDI: Provenance Information</p> <p>Representation Information</p>

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

CPP-027	File repair	As a way of handling validation errors or rendering errors, the TDA corrects structural issues identified in its files.	The AIP SHOULD include a record of repair actions that have been performed on the contents of the AIP. This is because repair actions may not be perfect or could require extra measures to be applied during future preservation or access to AIP contents.	PDI: Provenance Information Representation Information
CPP-028	Creation of derivative copies	The TDA generates derivative copies to address the specific needs of its Designated Community.	AIPs SHOULD include information on the provenance of the contents of the AIP, including any format conversions that have been applied to create derivative copies that are also held in the AIP (it is not mandatory for the AIP to contain access derivatives for use in DIPs, but this could be done if a TDA wants to package up their masters, normalised versions, access versions etc. all in one package) If the AIP contains both the original and normalised versions, then the AIP SHOULD identify which is which and the relationship between them, e.g. that File Y is an access derivative of File X.	PDI: Provenance Information Representation Information
CPP-029	Ingest	The TDA performs all operations necessary to transform a SIP into an AIP.	The AIP should contain a record of how it was constructed from one or more SIPs.	PDI: Provenance Information
CPP-030	Refreshment	The TDA replaces the Information Packages on a storage medium, copying them to a new medium and discarding the old one at the end of a storage medium's life cycle.	An AIP does not need to record details of how and where its contents are being stored including how storage systems and media are being managed. However, the AIP could include a record of storage refreshment and the checks done to ensure the migration between systems and/or media was successful. This is part of provenance information and can be useful if data corruption or loss is detected in the future and needs to be traced back to historical refreshment. An AIP MAY include a reference to an external system which contains information about the storage of the AIP. An AIP SHOULD include provenance information on refreshment.	PDI: context Information (e.g. what external database holds information on where the AIP is stored). This allows the AIP to be linked to Data Management Information (see OAIS 4.3.4), which is 'outside' of the AIP. PDI: Provenance Information

Requirements from FIDELIS TTRAM

[TTRAM](#) (Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix) from the FIDELIS project defines a set of activities/functions that are performed by trustworthy repositories. This is much broader in scope than the digital preservation focus of EDEN. Some, but not all, of the functions/activities in TTRAM will generate information

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

that will need to be retained in AIPs. Therefore, a cross-check of TTRAM with EDEN AIP requirements helps to (a) confirm that the AIP specification can accommodate all the relevant artefacts created by TTRAM processes, and (b) the use of the OAIS Information Model as the basis for an EDEN AIP doesn't have any gaps or limitations, i.e. the OAIS information model is sufficiently flexible and complete.

The TTRAM spreadsheet is large and still evolving. Some parts of the spreadsheet provide examples of information/evidence that is associated with each function/process and could be made transparent in order to help with assessment/assertions of trustworthiness. This isn't the same as information that might need to be held in an AIP, but it is nevertheless a useful input.

TTRAM Version v00.02:

- [Introduction and overview](#)
- [v00.02 Spreadsheet published 16 June 2025](#)

TTRAM ID	TTRAM Group	TTRAM Activity/ Function	TTRAM Description	TTRAM examples of Information which could be made transparent	Relevance to EDEN AIP requirements	Support in the OAIS Information Model
MX01	Context	Identification & Contact	Names, abbreviations and contact details for the organisation to provide reference information and context for the rest of the activities and functions.	Organisation Name Organisation Alternative Names Organisation Identifier(s) Contact details	AIPs SHOULD include a record of their origin, e.g. which organisation generated them.	PDI: Provenance Information
MX02	Context	Mission & Scope	Defining the purpose (or mission) of the organisation and the boundaries of activities for which the repository is responsible. Where activities involve partners or outsourced services, the organisation retains ultimate responsibility for the activities, functions and outcomes. Provides reference information and context for the rest of the activities and functions.	Organisation Mission Statement The LoRCAP offered by the repository Repository Type Designated Community Permitted/Restricted Object, Depositor and User Characteristics Geographic and linguistic coverage. Whether a repository is FAIR-enabling or endorses the TRUST or CARE Principles	It SHOULD be possible to assess the contents of AIPs against the FAIR principles as part of determining whether the repository is FAIR-enabling.	Content Information PDI
MX03	Digital Object Management	Conceive, Create, Collect	The stages of the research data lifecycle, before data enters a repository. Working	Any information or guidance provided to researchers about how to manage	AIPs COULD include any guidelines issued to the creators of the content	PDI: Context Information (e.g. references to deposit guidelines).

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

			with data or metadata creators and owners can help improve quality and highlight the benefits of curation, preservation and reuse.	their digital objects' data and metadata during the pre-repository phase. Funding Information Project Information Data Management Plan (DMP)	in the AIP, e.g. guidelines on quality, use of standards and specifications, required metadata etc.	Other Representation Information (e.g. guidelines that were followed pre-ingest)
MX04	Digital Object Management	Deposit & Appraisal	Accepting custody of digital objects from depositors, transferring responsibility to the repository. It may also include appraising offered or requested deposits to ensure they meet established criteria for acceptance.	Documentation of compliance criteria applied at the point of deposits, whether automated or manually applied and the degree to which they are required or optional. Collections Development and Appraisal Policy Deposit Compliance Criteria Deposit Procedures Acceptable/Preferred File Formats List ReAppraisal Plan, Data Management Plan Deposit licence (See also: Rights).	AIPs SHOULD include the deposit criteria that were applied when the AIP content was received. This allows checks to be done to confirm that the content still meets or exceeds these criteria.	PDI: Context Information (e.g. references to deposit criteria). PDI: Provenance Information (e.g. checks done against deposit criteria) PDI: Rights Information
MX05	Digital Object Management	Curation, Quality & Compliance	Ensuring digital objects reach a defined level of quality and standards compliance before they are made available for reuse.	Documentation of any initial curation steps taken after deposit to meet defined criteria for access and reuse and potentially to enable preservation, including any curation steps like conversions to file formats and any additions to metadata. Quality and Standards statements Standard operating procedures (SoP, Quality criteria) Compliance and Quality assurance policies and procedures	AIPs SHOULD include a record of any steps taken to check and ensure a defined level of quality has been met. The record should include what steps were taken, when, who by, using what tools, against which criteria etc.	PDI: Provenance Information

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

MX06	Digital Object Management	Discovery & Identification	Applying persistent identifiers and descriptive metadata to digital objects to support resource discovery. Providing discovery systems and making metadata available for harvesting.	Persistent identifiers used (ideally chosen from a controlled vocabulary) for objects, organisations, researchers, software etc, and information about whether all objects are persistently identified. Information about identification at a more granular level (files within objects, questions within surveys, variables within statistics). Links to resource discovery systems that the repository provides or third parties that index metadata harvested from the repository collection. Persistent Identifier system(s) PID Policy Discovery metadata and documentation Resource discovery catalogues Harvesting protocols (e.g. OAI-PMH)	AIPs MUST allow for persistent identifiers to be attached to the contents of the AIP. AIPs MUST allow for storage of all metadata necessary for future discovery of digital objects in the AIP.	PDI: Reference Information (identifiers) Representation Information (semantic and structural) Package Description (finding aids) PDI
MX07	Digital Object Management	Access	Determining the appropriate method of access—such as direct download or use within a secure remote environment—and facilitating user access accordingly. Access criteria are based on the characteristics of both the digital objects and the users., in alignment with rights management policies (see MX15 "Rights").	Access routes & methods, Access Management Policy Documentation of access routes and methods Licence and terms of access (See also: Rights)	See rights management below.	PDI: Rights Information
MX08	Digital Object Management	Reuse	Making, and keeping, digital objects usable and understandable depends on deposit, curation, and preservation activities. Facilitating reuse depends on understanding the needs and expectations of users, including—but not	References to artefacts including file formats, metadata and ontologies (potentially already mentioned under Deposit or Curation) that are specifically designed to enable reuse. Designated Community definitions,	AIPs MUST be able to hold all information necessary for future re-use of the AIP contents. This includes file formats, metadata, semantics and other information needed by a designated community of users in	Representation Information, PDI.

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

			limited to—identified 'designated communities', through ongoing external engagement (see MX20 "External Engagement"). Repositories may mediate reuse through secure remote access systems, safe rooms, or other tools that keep the digital objects fully or partially under the service provider's control.	digital object models. Terms and Conditions for Use Designated Community Consultation information.	order to understand and use the digital objects in the AIP.	
MX09	Digital Object Management	Workflows	Processes and activities for managing, changing and maintaining digital objects and their associated data and metadata in line with legal, ethical, policy, and other standards and operating procedures (see MX23 "Legal & Ethical" and MX14 "Policy & Standards Management").	Standard operating procedures, workflow/business process diagrams and documentation related to how the repository approaches digital object management.	AIPs SHOULD be able to hold documentation on the processes/procedures/workflows that are, or have been, used by an organisation to manage the content of the AIP.	OAIS Data Management Information (see OAIS 4.3.4) is an option for storing information on digital object management, but this is 'outside' of the AIP. For the contents of the AIP: External plans, processes and workflows could be referenced using PDI: Context Information. Execution can be recorded in PDI: Provenance Information.
MX10	Digital Object Management	Preservation	Monitoring both the technology landscape (see MX29 "Technical Infrastructure") and the user community (see MX20 "External Engagement") for any changes that could impact the usability or understanding (see MX08 "Reuse") of digital objects. When necessary, preservation actions are taken—such as migrating data formats, updating metadata (e.g., revising ontologies), or emulating the environment in which the digital object is used. These actions help ensure the long-term viability and continued accessibility of the digital object.	Preservation policies, strategies, plans and procedures that define how long artefacts will be preserved for, how potential preservation actions (emulation, file format updates, updates to semantic artefacts such as controlled vocabularies and ontologies) are approved and implemented. Interacts with re-appraisal criteria set during Deposit & Appraisal, the changing Technical Infrastructure Landscape over time, and how the ReUse needs of the community are monitored.	AIPs SHOULD be able to hold the preservation plans that have, or will be, applied to the contents of the AIP (e.g. file format migrations, metadata transformations, mappings to ontologies, the need for software tools or emulation for rendering etc.)	OAIS discusses preservation planning as part of the functional model, but has very little to say about where preservation plans are held, e.g. as part of an AIP. OAIS Data Management Information (see OAIS 4.3.4) is an option, but this is 'outside' of the AIP. For the contents of the AIP: External preservation plans could be referenced using PDI: Context Information. Preservation plans for future actions could be included in Representation

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

						Information (Other) as a description of what to do in order to interpret the object in the future. PDI: Provenance Information can be used to record the status and execution of preservation plans. PDI: Context Information (e.g. references to external file format registries and risks)
MX11	Digital Object Management	Provenance and Authenticity	Providing information about digital objects that details their history (provenance) and ensures their authenticity. Provenance and authenticity information can be captured at the point of deposit, generated during curation and preservation processes, and shared with data or metadata users.	Information about the creation, creators and history of the object requested at deposit. How the repository records information about changes to digital objects and what information is communicated externally (e.g. to end users).	AIPs MUST be able to hold provenance and authenticity information on their contents.	PDI: Provenance Information PDI: Fixity Information
MX12	Digital Object Management	Support	Providing guidance and responding to requests from depositors and users around deposit and appraisal, discovery, access and re-use of data and metadata.	Link to primary location where the repository provides supporting information or offers supporting services to depositors, users and others.	AIPs COULD include guidance that was provided to the depositors of the content in the AIP.	PDI: Context Information (e.g. references to external guidelines to depositors).
MX13	Organisational Infrastructure	Governance	The organisational hierarchies and processes by which the entity's mission is managed and executed.	Management and Decision documentation, organograms, management roles, role of host organisation, funders etc.	Out of scope	
MX14	Organisational Infrastructure	Policy & Standards	The adoption and development of policies, standards and other criteria to guide practice, aligned with governance structures (see MX13 "Governance") and operational workflows (see MX09 "Workflows"), and in compliance with the	Standards adoption criteria and decision making processes. Procedures for adopting and developing policies and standards, lists of policies and standards.	Out of scope	

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

			applicable legal and ethical framework (see MX23 "Legal and Ethical").			
MX15	Organisational Infrastructure	Rights	The management of permissions, prohibition, and obligations governing how digital objects are accessed and used by individuals and organisations, both within and outside the repository.	Rights Policy, Licences for deposit, access and reuse, non-compliance policy, sufficient rights to permit LoRCAP, rights related to succession plans.	AIPs MUST support inclusion of rights and licensing information that captures the permissions, prohibitions and obligations of anyone who accesses, uses or manages the contents of the AIP.	PDI: Rights Information
MX16	Organisational Infrastructure	Resources	The organisational hierarchies and processes by which the organisational entity's human and financial resources are obtained and managed. This includes a knowledge of and an effective deployment of human, financial and energy assets.	Budget and finance strategies, plans, reports and projections.	Out of scope	
MX17	Organisational Infrastructure	People & Expertise	The management of human resources to fulfil the mission. Includes ensuring that sufficient skills are available, internally or externally (see MX20 "External Engagement").	Skills Statement, Skills Development Plan, Staff Roles & Skills List,	Out of scope	
MX18	Organisational Infrastructure	Third Party Dependencies	Identifying and managing third-party organisations, hosts, partners, and other actors that are essential to operations, including the delivery of data or metadata services.	Lists of partners. Partnership Statement, Partner Management Plan, Contracts mapped to the functions and activities they provide for the organisation (e.g. a storage provider).	AIPs SHOULD allow records to be included in the AIP of organisations/third-parties that have been involved in the management and preservation of the contents of the AIP, for example use of third-party preservation services.	PDI: Provenance Information
MX19	Organisational Infrastructure	Continuity of Service	Ensuring business continuity by maintaining normal operations and preparing for disruptions. This includes non-technical processes (for technical, see MX29 "Technical Infrastructure") related to the organisation, digital object management (see MX09 "Workflows"),	Business Continuity Plan, Disaster Recovery Plan, Succession Plan	It SHOULD be possible to use AIPs as part of BCDR and Exit Strategies.	OAIS AIPs are intended to be self-describing and contain all the information necessary for their ongoing preservation and use.

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

			and security (see MX30 "Security"). It also covers recovery plans for events like service interruptions and disasters. Continuity includes succession planning for the end of a service.			
MX20	Organisational Infrastructure	External Engagement	Organisational interaction with external parties, including individuals, partner organisations, funders, and other relevant bodies.	Community Skills List, Community Engagement Plan, engagement with policy makers and funders, surveys of depositor and user needs.	Out of scope	
MX21	Organisational Infrastructure	Release & Publishing	The processes by which the organisation releases information artefacts (not deposited digital objects) such as publications, policies, and other content. It includes publishing information that provides evidence for external assessments (see MX24 "Criteria, Assessment, Improvement") and supports external engagement (see MX20 "External Engagement").	Records management policy, records retention schedule, publication approval process	AIPs SHOULD allow for retention schedules to be included in the AIP that apply to the contents of the AIP.	PDI: Provenance Information (e.g. what's been deleted) PDI: Rights Information (e.g. agreements/permissions to retain/delete content) PDI: Context Information (e.g. reference to external retention schedules and records management policies).
MX22	Organisational Infrastructure	Interoperability	The protocols and processes by which people, processes, technologies and digital objects effectively interact with others, both within and across organisational entities.	Links to and documentation of any machine accessible routes to data and/or metadata. e.g. API's. OAI-PMH	It MUST be possible to exchange AIPs between organisations/systems without loss of content or meaning.	All parts of the OAIS Information Model for AIPs!
MX23	Organisational Infrastructure	Legal & Ethical	The legal and ethical obligations that the organisation must be aware of and adhere to.	Legal Statement, Ethical Statement, Compliance Policy, Legislation List, Ethical Guidance List, Compliance SoP	AIPs SHOULD be able to hold any legal/ethical/compliance restrictions or requirements that apply to the contents of the AIP.	PDI: Rights Information
MX24	Organisational Infrastructure	Criteria, Assessment, Improvement	The processes used to assess compliance with standards, policies, and procedures, along with identifying actions for continuous and targeted improvement.	Change Management, Self-Assessments, Certification	AIPs MUST allow for comparison with the OAIS Information Model so that compliance to the standard can be assessed.	OAIS Packing Information

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

MX25	Organisational Infrastructure	Analysis & Impact	The analysis of internal data and external information to verify and demonstrate that the organisation is effectively fulfilling its mission (see MX02 "Mission & Scope").	Business information analysis, identification and validation of external impact.	Out of scope.	
MX26	Organisational Infrastructure	Training	Leveraging internal expertise to train data and metadata producers, owners, depositors, and users. Training can cover the entire digital object management lifecycle, from the conception of research to the reuse of data and metadata. It also includes training for internal staff, as well as for peer organisations, partners, and third parties.	Link to primary location where the organisation provides training materials and/or details of training programmes.	Out of scope.	
MX27	Organisational Infrastructure	Research & Development (R&D)	Projects and other activities outside current operations, routine maintenance and upgrades. This can include new approaches to data, metadata, business processes, technology, security, and research infrastructure.	Documentation of project, specification, development and delivery processes. Links to information about projects the organisation is involved with. How products move from 'in development' to 'in production'	Out of scope.	
MX28	Technology	Storage & Integrity	The methods used to store and replicate digital objects' data and metadata, including the validation of replicated copies and the restoration of data from backups in case of errors.	Storage Documentation, integrity measures used, approach to integrity checking.	AIPs MUST be able to hold fixity information, e.g. checksums, that can be used to support the long-term safe storage of the AIP.	PDI: Fixity Information
MX29	Technology	Technical Infrastructure	The comprehensive provision of hardware, software, and IT service management to support the organisation's entity. Monitoring the user community technical needs and broader technical landscape to update and maintain levels of technical service (see MX08 ReUse).	Technical Infrastructure Statement, Technical Infrastructure Plan, IT Service Management methodologies. 'Service Catalogues' (cf: FitSM)	AIPs SHOULD be able to record the technical infrastructure that was, or is being used, for their ongoing preservation and management, for example details of what preservation tools and systems have been used.	PDI: Provenance Information (e.g. actions taken on content of AIP) PDI: Context Information (e.g. references to external systems used to hold/preserve/manage the API)

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

MX30	Security	Security	Ensuring security across the organisation’s infrastructure, digital object management, and systems. Security also extends to the boundary between the repository and external entities, including dependencies on third parties.	Information Security Statement, Information Security Plan, related certifications (e.g. ISO27001)	Out of scope? Maybe the AIP should allow for a record to be retained of any unauthorised or uncontrolled access to the contents that could have resulted in alterations/deletions/additions?	PDI: Provenance Information.
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Requirements from F-UJI FAIR data assessment

AIPs should contain all the information that is needed to be able to understand and use the data within them. This means AIPs need to be able to hold everything needed for data to be FAIR. One way to address this is for AIPs to be able to hold all the information that is needed to satisfy the [F-UJI](#) FAIR assessment metrics. The latest version (18 March 2025) is [V0.8 of the FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics](#).

Note that it is not a requirement for a system that stores, manages or provides access to AIPs to itself support all the FAIR metrics. Rather the contents of the AIP must contain everything needed to allow the contents of the AIP (maybe after conversion into DIPs) to be provided in a FAIR way. For example, AIPs don't themselves need to support a standard protocol for accessing their contents (although this is probably a good idea anyway). But AIPs do need to contain everything needed by a repository that does provide discovery and access services.

F-UJI Version: [V0.8 of the FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics](#)

FAIRsFAIR Identifier	Name	Relevance to EDEN AIP requirements
FsF-F1-01D	Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.	Data in an AIP MUST have one or more globally unique identifiers. Identifiers can be used at any level, e.g. whole datasets down to individual bitstreams.
FsF-F1-02D	Data is assigned a persistent identifier.	Identifiers for data in an AIP MUST be persistent.
FsF-F2-01M	Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.	AIP MUST contain core descriptive metadata. This MUST be machine accessible and readable.
FsF-F3-01M	Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.	Metadata is linked to data through the use of identifiers.
FsF-F4-01M	Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines.	It MUST be possible to extract metadata from an AIP so that the contents (data) in the AIP can be determined.

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

FsF-A1-01M	Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.	The AIP must be able to hold access rights information about when access to the data in the AIP is allowed.
FsF-A1-02M	Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol	It MUST be possible for descriptive metadata in the AIP to be associated with an identifier.
FsF-A1-03D	Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol	It SHOULD be possible to access contents of the AIP using a standardised protocol.
FsF-A2-01M	Metadata remains available, even if the data is no longer available.	NOT APPLICABLE. This metric has been 'suspended' at the data object level in the FAIRsFAIR metrics.
FsF-I1-01M	Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.	It MUST be possible to use whatever formal knowledge representation language is appropriate for a Designated Community.
FsF-I2-01M	Metadata uses semantic resources.	An AIP MUST support the inclusion of, or linking to, semantic resources (ontologies, thesauri, taxonomies etc.).
FsF-I3-01M	Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities.	An AIP MUST allow contents (data and metadata) to be linked to related datasets, prior versions, related resources etc. and to do so using typed relationships (e.g. DataCite relation types).
FsF-R1-01MD	Metadata specifies the content of the data.	An AIP MUST support metadata that describes the characteristics of the data in the AIP (e.g. file format, technical metadata etc.).
FsF-R1.1-01M	Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.	The AIP MUST be able to hold licensing information about the restrictions on the use of the data in the AIP.
FsF-R1.2-01M	Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.	The AIP MUST be able to hold provenance information on the contents of the AIP (data and metadata). Provenance information SHOULD use recognised standards, e.g. PROV-O.
FsF-R1.3-01M	Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data.	The AIP MUST allow for metadata to use formats/standards appropriate to and recommended by a designated community.
FsF-R1.3-02D	Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community.	The AIP MUST allow for data to be held using formats/standards that are appropriate to and recommended by a designated community.

Requirements from EOSC TF LTDP Report

The EOSC Task Force on Long Term Data Preservation issued a [report that contains recommendations and assertions on how digital preservation can be improved in EOSC](#). The report identifies several gaps that need to be filled, for example improvements in transparency for how digital objects are being preserved, the ability to specify and apply different levels of care to digital objects, and the use and extension of CoreTrustSeal as the basis of TDR assessment and certification. Several of these areas can be supported through holding evidence and information in AIPs, for example allowing them to be used as part of assessment and transparency.

Some of the recommendations from the EOSC TF on LTDP are provided in the table below including how they can be supported by suitable AIPs. The focus is recommendations by the TF where there are currently gaps, which helps identify AIP requirements for EOSC that may not be met by existing standards and specification.

EOSC TF LTPD recommendation or assertion	Category	Relevance to EDEN AIP requirements
7. The Principles that digital objects should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) define desirable outcomes of digital objects' care.	Repositories and the Digital Object Lifecycle	AIPs should be able to record evidence of FAIR assessment and actions that aim to ensure that digital objects remain FAIR.
12. Different data and metadata services are required to support research across the full digital object lifecycle.	Repositories and the Digital Object Lifecycle	It should be possible to exchange AIPs in whole or in part between TDAs and third-parties that can provide digital preservation services.
17. Repositories benefit from being transparent on their current level of storage, curation and preservation practice, as this increases trust by the user and funders.	Repositories and the Digital Object Lifecycle	AIPs can contain the information / evidence needed to support transparency, for example provenance information that shows that good preservation practice is being followed.
19. @Repositories should specify all the levels of care they apply to objects within their collection, including through repository and digital object registry metadata	Curation & Preservation Levels	AIPs should be able to record the level of care that has been assigned to them or needs to be applied. AIPs should be able to record actions taken on their contents when applying a given level of care.
20. @Digital objects should include metadata that specify their level of care and the timeframes or criteria for reappraisal of the level of care*	Curation & Preservation Levels	AIPs should be able to record the level of care that has been assigned to them, needs to be applied, or has been applied (these are not necessarily the same). AIPs should be able to record information on their appraisal and re-appraisal.
21. Objects may be made FAIR before deposit in a repository (Level D) or made FAIR by initial curation within the repository (Level C).	FAIR + Time	AIPs should be able to record curation that has happened within the repository to make the contents FAIR

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

22. As technical infrastructure and the needs of user communities evolve, digital objects that were initially made FAIR may require additional preservation actions over time to ensure they remain FAIR.	FAIR + Time	AIPs should be able to record preservation actions that have been applied within the repository to make the contents FAIR or to ensure the contents remain FAIR. This includes the outcomes of these actions, for example an assessment of FAIRness.
24. @FAIR-enabling practices undertaken by repositories should be made transparent to users and funders to increase trust in services*	FAIR + Time	AIPs can be used to provide evidence that appropriate actions have been taken to ensure content is and remains FAIR. This helps provide transparency.
26. Preservation actions include any action on a digital objects' data (e.g. format updates), metadata (e.g. schema updates) or on the environment provided to interact with the digital object (e.g. emulation) to ensure the object retains desirable characteristics (e.g. FAIRness). 27. Preservation outcomes are demonstrated by an object maintaining desirable characteristics (e.g. FAIRness) over time.	Preservation Systems, Actions & Outcomes	AIPs should include a record of preservation actions and their outcomes.
32. The LTDP TF reasserts the conclusion of previous EOSC-relevant papers and groups that the CoreTrustSeal provides an appropriate mechanism to define core expectations of TDRs and an exemplar for offering assessment and certification services*. 33. With the exception of the requirements for offering preservation services (CoreTrustSeal Requirement 09) and considering reuse (CoreTrustSeal Requirement 13) the CoreTrustSeal is relevant to all repositories.	Trustworthy Digital Repositories (TDR) and other Data and Metadata Services	AIPs should support the requirements of CoreTrustSeal
39. @Additional work is needed to define different types of digital object systems, the activities and functions they undertake, and the levels of care they provide for data and metadata*.	Trustworthy Digital Repositories (TDR) and other Data and Metadata Services	The range of types of digital object, the levels of care they need, and the techniques required to provide this care are not yet fully defined. Therefore, AIPs should be flexible enough to accommodate corresponding metadata and provenance.
43. Indicators, metrics and tests can be designed to assess compliance with standards. 44. Standards may be used to support, self-, peer- or third-party assessment approaches. 45. Assessments can be used to acknowledge quality (e.g. certification of repositories) and help service providers understand their current state and plan actions for future priorities and goals.	Standards, Assessment, Certification & Alignment	AIPs should be able to contain the information needed to support assessment, including through metrics and tests, and allow these assessments to be done internally or by third-parties. For example, by providing evidence that a repository has applied good preservation practice and is conformant with standards such as OAIS.
54. @Efforts by repositories and other data services to share transparent information about their functions, activities and objects should be rewarded by targeted investment for improvement*.	Outcomes, Judgement and Gatekeeping	AIPs can provide the information needed to support transparency, for example provenance information that records quality assessment and the application of preservation actions.

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

55. @No repository or digital object should be unnecessarily excluded from any part of EOSC	Outcomes, Judgement and Gatekeeping	AIPs should provide flexibility for repositories to use metadata and data standards that are appropriate to them or are already in use. Mandating specific metadata and data standards for the contents of AIPs could cause unnecessary exclusion of repositories who are not able to adopt such standards.
57. A long-tail of data exists that has not been brought into a managed storage, curation, or preservation system.	Retention, Appraisal & Re-Appraisal	AIPs need to be flexible in the types of metadata and data that they can contain.
58. Any decision taken to evaluate a digital object with a view to delete it, retain it or assign or change a level of care is an appraisal decision. 61. @Retention and reappraisal decisions and timescales, including guaranteed preservation timescales, should be transparent.	Retention, Appraisal & Re-Appraisal	AIPs should be able to record appraisal decisions and provide evidence of appraisal as part of transparency.
62. Transparency of metadata, supporting artefacts (policies, preservation plans, data management plans) and digital objects fosters understanding, interoperability and continuous improvement between peer services. 65. @Each repository should be transparent about the levels of care provided*. 66. @Each object should have a clear level of care associated with the repositories that take responsibility for them*. 68. @Registries of repositories and other data services should align metadata about levels of care and supporting information*. 69. @Registries of digital objects should align metadata relating to retention periods, appraisal periods and levels of curation and preservation.	Transparency of Services, Artefacts and Levels of Care for Objects	AIP content can support transparency, for example by holding information and evidence of levels of care. AIPs need to support interoperability, for example by having clear and machine readable descriptions of their contents and the metadata and data standards being used. This includes retention management, appraisal, levels of care, preservation actions applied etc. This supports the need to do transformations and cross-walks as part of content exchange.
82. Roles and responsibilities include the early definition of preservation actions in a data management plan. These include multi-copy/multi-location redundancy, integrity, data protection, digital object design, provenance information, appraisal criteria, desirable retention and preservation periods, and target repositories.	Roles and Responsibilities	Many of the aspects described for preservation and data management planning would be done within a TDA but not recorded within AIPs. However, there is the potential for AIPs to be as self-describing as possible, for example containing their own data management plans, retention information, appraisal criteria etc.
112. @“EOSC cannot rely on a single generic canon of ‘digital preservation practice’. Instead, workflows should leverage large scale infrastructures while remaining faithful to discipline-specific requirements”.	Recommendations at European Level	The AIP specification used in EDEN should be flexible so it can accommodate discipline-specific data types and approaches. The specification should not mandate or depend upon a specific approach to digital preservation practice.
118. @Support the development of digital rights management standards and mechanisms that enable the transition of digital objects and repositories’ licences towards machine-actionable, scalable interoperability including:	Recommendations at European Level	AIPs should support inclusion of rights and licensing information that covers the full breadth of the data lifecycle including preservation of data with repositories and its future uses by designated communities. Both the rights and data can be complex.

D.2.1 Annex – EOSC EDEN AIP Services

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| a. Granular and dynamic digital objects. | | |
| b. Complex organisational partnerships and outsourcing. | | |
| c. Full lifecycle research data management, storage, curation and preservation. | | |

The analysis above of the EOSC TF LTDP recommendations has several key themes:

- The data and metadata that needs preservation in EOSC TDRs is diverse, can be very complex, involves discipline specific standards and techniques, and can't be made to fit into a single generic model of digital preservation. This requires AIPs to be very flexible in the breadth and type of information they can contain.
- The drive towards transparency plus the need to be able to assess repositories against CoreTrustSeal, good preservation practice, and FAIRness of their holdings can all be supported by the recording of corresponding information and evidence within AIPs.
- There is a wide range of information that can, and should, be held in AIPs in addition to the research data that needs to be preserved. This includes levels of care, quality assessments and appraisal, preservation plans, preservation actions, rights and licensing, and initial and ongoing curation. The specifics of some of this information (e.g. formats, schemas, vocabularies) does not yet exist or is under development. This in turn requires AIPs to be flexible and extensible in the information they can hold.